

VME MESTRA Rev C Specification

Content

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	6
1.1	Purpose.....	6
1.2	Scope.....	6
1.3	Definitions, acronyms and abbreviations.....	6
1.4	References.....	6
2	Overall description.....	7
2.1	Principle of Operation.....	7
2.2	System Configuration.....	7
2.2.1	Monitors.....	7
2.2.2	SU Signals.....	8
2.2.3	Display Signals.....	9
2.2.4	RF Signals.....	9
2.2.5	Experiment.....	9
2.2.6	LogCAM Signals.....	9
2.2.7	Interlock Signals.....	9
2.2.8	Inhibit Signals.....	10
2.2.9	Line Drivers & Signal Converters.....	10
2.2.10	Transmission Calculations.....	10
2.2.11	Risks.....	10
3	Concept.....	11
3.1	Overview.....	11
3.1.1	Functional Concept.....	12
3.1.2	Electronics Concept.....	13
3.1.3	System Concept.....	14
3.1.4	Commissioning Concept.....	15
4	Sub-Systems.....	17
4.1	Preamplifier.....	17
4.1.1	Power Budget.....	18
4.2	Crate.....	19
4.3	IOxOS IFC1210.....	20
4.4	IOxOS ADC3110.....	20
4.5	Software Architecture.....	21
4.6	Digital Down Converter (MESTRA).....	22
4.6.1	Architecture.....	23
4.6.2	Implementation.....	23
4.7	CPU Signal Processing (MESTRA).....	25
4.8	EPICS Interface.....	25
4.9	Interlock Interface.....	36

4.9.1	Interlock Components	37
4.9.2	Interlocks Slot#1.....	40
4.9.3	Interlocks Slot#2.....	41
4.9.4	Interlocks Slot#3.....	41
4.10	EtherCAT Interface	41
4.10.1	EtherCAT Components	42
4.10.2	EtherCAT Slot#1	49
4.10.3	EtherCAT Slot#2	53
4.10.4	EtherCAT Slot#3	56
4.11	Transmission Calculations (STRAM)	59
4.11.1	Transmissions Slot#1	68
4.11.2	Transmissions Slot#2.....	75
4.11.3	Transmissions Slot#3.....	77
5	Commissioning.....	80
5.1	EtherCAT CoE Static Configuration	80
5.2	Preamplifier tuning	80
5.3	System Startup.....	80
5.4	EtherCAT Debugging	80
6	Appendix	82
6.1	System Specifications	82
6.2	Cable List	85
6.3	Spare Parts	87
6.4	Cost Estimation	87
6.5	Source Directories.....	88
6.6	Document History.....	88
Figures		
Figure 1	VME MESTRA Picture	7
Figure 2	MESTRA Block Diagram (simplified)	12
Figure 3	Electronics Mechanical Diagram (MM = Multi Mode optical fibre).....	13
Figure 4	System Concept.....	15
Figure 5	LNA Mini-Circuits ZX60-P103LN+	17
Figure 6	Preamplifier Front Assembly	18
Figure 7	Preamplifier Box.....	18
Figure 8	Temperature at different fan-speed settings (TreNew)	19
Figure 9	ADC3110 Architecture	21
Figure 10	Digital Processing Architecture	22
Figure 11	DDC Architecture – One out of 8 channels	23
Figure 12	CIC-CFIR-FIR Transfer Function (Matlab)	24
Figure 13	Transfer Function at 6 th harmonics (measured)	24
Figure 14	Interlock Implementation for one out of two slots	37

Figure 15 Din-Rail Int	38
Figure 16 Din-Rail Interlock Unit Enclosure	38
Figure 17 Din-Rail Interlock Unit Block Diagram	39
Figure 18 Din-Rail Interlock Unit Layout	39
Figure 19 INLK J5 (LEMO Front View – PCB vertical)	40
Figure 20 Beckhoff EK1100 EtherCAT Coupler	42
Figure 21 Beckhoff EK1521 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction	43
Figure 22 Beckhoff EK1501 EtherCAT Coupler with ID switch, fibre optic	43
Figure 23 Beckhoff EL2521 1-channel pulse train output terminal RS422	44
Figure 24 Beckhoff EL4102 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 bit	44
Figure 25 Beckhoff EL4112 2-channel analog output terminal 0.20mA, 16 bit	45
Figure 26 Beckhoff EL3314 4-channel thermocouple input terminal	45
Figure 27 Beckhoff EL9505 Power supply terminal 5V	46
Figure 28 Beckhoff EL2124 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC	46
Figure 29 Beckhoff EL1124 4-channel digital input terminal 5V DC	47
Figure 30 LEG SU3-2 Signalumwandler RS422-TTL	48
Figure 31 EtherCAT Topology Slot#1	49
Figure 32 EtherCAT Topology Slot#2	53
Figure 33 EtherCAT Topology Slot#3	56

Tables

Table 1 Cavity Monitors	8
Table 2 RF Signals	9
Table 3 Transmission Calculations	10
Table 4 EPICS Interface Specifications ZPSAF66-VMEIFC Slot#1	29
Table 5 EPICS Interface Specifications ZPSAF67-VMEIFC Slot#2	33
Table 6 Connector Specifications J1, J2, J3 and J4 – Type: IDG-A	40
Table 7 Connector Specifications J5 – Type: LEMO EPG.00.303.NLN	40
Table 8 Interlock Implementation EC1 Slot#1	41
Table 9 Interlock Implementation EC2 Slot#2	41
Table 10 Interlock Implementation EC3 Slot#3	41
Table 11 EtherCAT Specifications Slot#1	52
Table 12 EtherCAT Specifications Slot#2	56
Table 13 EtherCAT Specifications Slot#3	58
Table 14 EL2521 CoE Settings	80
Table 15 Measurement Specifications	82
Table 16 Crate Slot Assignment	82
Table 17 Analog Input Assignment Preamplifier (PA)	83
Table 18 Analog Input Assignment ADC3110 (S1.FMC1/S2.FMC1)	84
Table 19 Cable List	87
Table 20 Cost Estimation - Material	87

Table 21 Source Directories.....	88
Table 22 Document History.....	88

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The primary objective of this “specification document” is to specify the VME MESTRA measurement system. The specification defines the functionality on a design-level. The intended audience is software and hardware developers developing the system, but the overview chapters are targeting system engineers using the measurement system.

1.2 Scope

The VME MESTRA measurement system is developed as a replacement for the existing Camac MESTRA/STRAM electronics. The new system is compatible with the sensors installed in the PSI high-energy proton accelerator. The motivation for developing a new measurement system is that the existing system is getting very old (from approx. 1986).

The purpose of the system is to measure the beam current at several places in the HIPA machine and distribute these current signals to the machine electronics. It also calculates beam losses (transmission) and generates interlocks if required.

1.3 Definitions, acronyms and abbreviations

This document is based on the IEEE Std-830-1998 Recommended Practice for Software Requirements Specifications and adapted to the needs for a system design specification.

Term	Meaning
DDC	Digital Down Converter
DPRAM	Dual ported RAM
EPICS	Experimental Physics and Industrial Control System – utilizing a server/client communication model based on Ethernet
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
HIPA	High Intensity Proton Machine at PSI
IFC1210	VME Intelligent FPGA Carrier Board from IOxOS
NC	No Connect
VME / VMEbus	Versa Module Europa / VERSAmodule Eurocard bus

1.4 References

[1] IEEE Std-830-1998 Recommended Practice for Software Requirements Specifications

2 Overall description

TBD

Figure 1 VME MESTRA Picture

2.1 Principle of Operation

Inside the HIPA machine there are installed several “reentrant resonant cavities” that are tuned at the 2nd harmonics of the machine. These sensors are delivering an electrical signal at 101.2656MHz that is proportional to the beam current. The signal at the cavity is typically -90dBm at 1uA current.

The VME MESTRA system is measuring the amplitude of the RF-signals from the cavities. The amplitude is converted into a digital signal that corresponds to the proton beam current. This digital signal is then distributed to digital-analog converters and as EPICS channels to the control system.

2.2 System Configuration

The HIPA CAMAC MESTRA and STRAM system is built up of several cards that are connected with a high number of wires. There are a total of 14 MESTRA cards and 5 STRAM cards. The purpose of the VME MESTRA is to replace this functionality.

The task of the MESTRA card is to transform the amplitude of the 101MHz RF-signal from the cavity into a proportional voltage signal. This is done with an analog circuit in the old system. The voltage signal is today either distributed directly as a voltage or as a frequency signal. The VFC (Voltage to Frequency Converter) is used as a kind of ADC converter.

The STRAM cards have got ADC converters to digitize the voltage signals from the MESTRA. The STRAM card is calculating the transmission for selected monitors at 5kHz frequency. If the transmission is outside the allowed value an interlock is activated.

In the VME MESTRA system there are only two VME cards for the processing of the RF-signals. Each card is replacing 8 MESTRA cards and up to 4 STRAM cards. The signal processing is digital and the RF-signals are converted with under-sampling at 50Msps. The output signals are implemented with a fieldbus system called EtherCAT.

2.2.1 Monitors

(Based on the document: “Current and Transmission Measurement” dated 08.03.2001, P.-A. Dupperex)

Monitor	Max. Cur. [mA]	Frequency	Voltage	Interlock Output	Inhibit Output	Voltage Output#1	Voltage Output#2	Frequency Output
MXC1	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MXC2	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MNC3	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MHC1	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MHC2	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MHC3	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MHC4	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MHC5	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MHC6	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MBC1	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	?	?	?
MBC1B	2.5	100kHz/1mA	10V/2.5mA	?	?	cRIO UCN	?	?
MYC1	0.25	100kHz/0.1mA	10V/0.25mA	?	?	?	?	?
MYC2	0.25	100kHz/0.1mA	10V/0.25mA	?	?	?	?	?

Table 1 Cavity Monitors

2.2.2 SU Signals

Source: Otmar Morath (01.12.2014):

Experimental area entrance WEHA.17.01

Display

MHC1, signal level: ?

Cable number: 01-8297 B11.11

Room WBGA C42

Display for SINQ

MHC6, MHC1, signal level: frequency

Cable number: ?

Display for UCN

MBC1, signal level current

Cable number: ?

All display signals are slow and can technically be distributed as EPICS signals.

NOTE: MHC1 and MHC6 are in the future only available as EPICS channels!

UCN – WMFA

Connected to interface box UM1124 4603.1

Signals unknown. Probably frequency-current converter installed

Cable number: 50012-3058; 50012-3057

TBD

2.2.3 Display Signals

Old system:

Source: Rudolf Hugi (02.12.2014)

The following signals are used by the "Hallenanzeige"

MHC4, MHC6, Signal level: 0..10V (2.5mA)

Connected to interface box in B11.5 (WBGA Injektor 1 Versorgungsraum)

Signals are digitized and distributed by RS-422 to the displays.

New solution:

MHC4 and MHC6 are distributed by EPICS network.

Responsible:

Network: Hubert Lutz

Display: Martin Gasche

2.2.4 RF Signals

Source: Stefan Mair (07.01.2015)

Monitor	Description	Scaling	Building	Rack	Cable
MXC1	Display	0..10V (0..2.5mA)	WIHA/EG	G48.1	56-87 ?
MXC1	Nachführung des Begrenzerpegels (A-Regler)	0..10V (0..2.5mA)	WIHA/EG	G48.1	56-87 ?
MXC1	Umschaltkriterium für den Reflexionspegel	0..10V (0..2.5mA)	WIHA/EG	G48.1	56-87 ?
MHC1	Display	0..10V (0..2.5mA)	WSGA/OG	S87.12 s87.13	04-6141 ?
MHC1	Gegenvector aus Strahlstromkompensation (Flattop) Nachführung des Begrenzerpegels (A-Regler)	0..10V (0..2.5mA)	WSGA/OG	S87.31	04-6142 ?
MHC1	Umschaltkriterium für den Reflexionspegel	0..10V (0..2.5mA)	WSGA/OG	S87.32	04-6143 ?

Table 2 RF Signals

NOTE: Details from Markus Schneider concerning dynamic requirements.

NOTE: MXC1 and MHC1B are in the future available as remote 0..10V signals for compatibility.

2.2.5 Experiments

Signals TBD.

MHC1, MBC1, MHC4: Signal level: frequency

2.2.6 LogCAM Signals

LogCAM compatible LogIV outputs are available on remote EtherCAT I/O blocks.

2.2.7 Interlock Signals

Redundant PSI interlock signals are available for the Run-Permit-System (RPS) and the Schnelle-Abschalt-System (SAS).

2.2.8 Inhibit Signals

TBD

2.2.9 Line Drivers & Signal Converters

TBD

2.2.10 Transmission Calculations

Name	Description	Formulas (simplified)
MHTR1	EHT	$MHC1 - (MBC1 + MHC2)$
MHTR2	P-channel	$MHC2 - MHC3, MHC3 - MHC4, MHC4 - MHC5$
MHTR3	SINQ	$MHC5 - MHC6$
MHTR2-M	TGE Megapie	$MHC4 - MHC5$
MNTR	Ring	$MNC3 - MHC1$

Table 3 Transmission Calculations

2.2.11 Risks

The dynamic requirements of the RF control are unknown. The new system has higher group delay due to the 5kHz processing of analog output signals.

3 Concept

3.1 Overview

The VME MESTRA measurement system consists of several Sub-Systems:

- Preamplifier
- Digitizer (ADC)
- Digital Down Converters (DDC)
- Current Calculations
- Transmission Calculations
- EPICS Interface
- Interlock Outputs
- Current Outputs

3.1.1 Functional Concept

Figure 2 MESTRA Block Diagram (simplified)

The VME MESTRA is based on direct under-sampling of the RF signal coming from the cavity. Mixing and low-pass filtering is done digitally in an FPGA fabric. The calculation of the transmission is done on a floating-point CPU.

The amplified beam cavity RF signals are connected to a digitizer. The digitized signals are then processed with a digital down converter (DDC). The DDC is delivering two orthogonal signals called I/Q that allows the calculation of a signal proportional to the beam current. This signal has to be calibrated by the control system to deliver the absolute current level.

The absolute currents are sent to the EPICS interface and used for transmission calculations. The STRAM transmission calculations are checking if the current level is in the expected range. If out of range interlock signals are activated.

The absolute currents are also distributed inside the HIPA machine in form of voltage or frequency signals.

The attenuation of the cellflex-cables increases with temperature. It is therefore foreseen to measure the cable temperature and add a linear compensation to the measured current value.

3.1.2 Electronics Concept

Figure 3 Electronics Mechanical Diagram (MM = Multi Mode optical fibre)

The mechanical concept is based on 19" rack components and DIN-rail components. There is one common 16-channel 19" pre-amplifier and one 7-slot VME crate populated with two controllers. Each controller has a local EtherCAT I/O block connected by electrical Ethernet. There is further support for up to four remote EtherCAT I/O blocks for each controller. These I/O

blocks are connected by multi-mode optical fibre and may be placed up to 2000m from the controller.

3.1.3 System Concept

The system concept is implemented to reduce the length of electrical wiring. This is done to reduce electromagnetic interference and reduce the effect of temperature dependency.

The new VME MESTRA main controllers are placed in BGA/A31 B11.12. First it will be operated in parallel with the CAMAC MESTRA system in B11.11. Later on VME MESTRA is moved to the B11.11 rack.

Locally at the VME MESTRA main controllers there are I/O terminals for debugging the currents, temperature measurements and interlock signals.

The electrical process I/O signals are implemented with remote I/O connected by means of fibre optical links. The concept is to place the I/O terminals where the signals are used. This avoids long electrical wires.

Figure 4 System Concept

3.1.4 Commissioning Concept

The goal of the commissioning phase is to avoid downtime of the machine and maintain machine safety during commissioning. To fulfil this goal it is planned to operate the old CAMAC MESTRA/STRAM system and the new VME MESTRA system in parallel for a period of one year.

During shutdown 2015/2016 all cellflex cables for the VME MESTRA have to be installed. The test-signal of the cavities are connected to the VME MESTRA system and used as beam signals. This will allow operating the existing system and the VME MESTRA in parallel.

The VME MESTRA is then integrated in the control system and configured for parallel operation to the CAMAC system. This will require implementation of the calibration algorithm. As soon as the system parameters are configured properly the interlocks are integrated in the machine interlock system. Other sub-systems can now start using the output signals from the VME MESTRA system.

During shutdown 2016/2017 the cavity signals to the CAMAC system are switched to the VME MESTRA system. The VME MESTRA is now operated as a replacement of the CAMAC system. When the reliability of the VME MESTRA is confirmed and all external signals are transferred to the VME MESTRA system, the CAMAC system can be shut down. All EPICS channels of the CAMAC MESTRA/STRAM are now replaced with the VME MESTRA EPICS channels.

4 Sub-Systems

This chapter gives a more detailed description of the sub-systems of the VME MESTRA system.

4.1 Preamplifier

The preamplifier is amplifying the RF signals from the machine. The outputs from the preamplifier are connected directly to the ADC3110 ADC card. One preamplifier consists of 16 channels.

There are 19x LNA's in one 19" carrier with a common power-supply. The front-end amplifiers are implemented with Mini-Circuits E-PHEMT amplifiers with very low noise figure. The power supply is implemented with a high quality AC/DC converter from TDK-Lambda suitable for 24/7 operation.

Specification:

- | | |
|--------------------------------------|------------------|
| • 19x LNA Mini-Circuits ZX60-P103LN+ | 9.0W |
| • 1x AC/DC TDK-Lambda HWS-30A-5/A | 30% typical load |
| • Noise Figure: | 0.6dB typical |
| • Gain: | +25dB |

Figure 5 LNA Mini-Circuits ZX60-P103LN+

Figure 6 Preamplifier Front Assembly

Figure 7 Preamplifier Box

4.1.1 Power Budget

The signal strength from the cavity is approx. -90dBm at 1uA beam current. Some inputs have a maximum current of 2.5mA, others have 0.25mA maximum current. An upgrade to maximum 3mA beam current has to be possible.

Typical power budget with maximum 2500uA beam current (OUT1..OUT13)

- Sensor @ 1uA: -90dBm
- Beam 2500uA: +68.0dB → -22.0dBm

- ½" Cellflex 150m: -3dB → -25.0dBm
- 1st Amplifier: +25dB → +0.0dBm (0.63Vp-p, 32% of ADC max)

Typical power budget with maximum 250uA beam current (OUT14..OUT16)

- Sensor @ 1uA: -90dBm
- Beam 250uA: +48.0dB → -42.0dBm
- ½" Cellflex 150m: -3dB → -45.0dBm
- 1st Amplifier: +25dB → -20.0dBm
- 2nd Amplifier: +25dB → +5.0dBm (1.1Vp-p, 56% of ADC max)

4.2 Crate

The implementation strategy is to reuse system components that are already used at PSI or use standard components available on the market. The development of new PCBs is avoided.

The system is designed to fit into a 19" rack. The digital electronics is based on VME64x.

The crate shall fulfill the power, shielding and cooling requirements of the controller boards. The only parameter that is expected to be critical is the cooling requirements.

Prototype test has been done with a TreNew PSI crate V1.10. These tests showed that the temperature of the IFC1210 Central FPGA is the critical component. Operating in automatic mode (default mode) the default minimum fan speed of 30% was found a bit low. It is therefore proposed to set FAN_MIN_SPEED to 50%.

Figure 8 Temperature at different fan-speed settings (TreNew)

4.3 IOxOS IFC1210

For the digital signal processing a board with FPGA for the DDC and a floating-point CPU for angel calculations is required. The IOxOS IFC1210 has been selected as carrier board as this board is already well integrated in the PSI infrastructure.

The IFC1210 offers an FPGA that is big enough for 8 high-resolution DDC channels. It further offers slots for FMC cards suitable for high speed digitizers. The supported Embedded Linux operating system is supporting the 5kHz synchronized processing required for the RF measurement application. There is further EPICS support for the board.

The overall VME MESTRA system requires two IFC1210 boards.

Key specifications:

- Freescale P2020 1.2GHz dual core floating-point CPU
- Xilinx Virtex-6 XC6VLX130T FPGA
- 2x FMC slots
- Embedded Linux (PREEMPT_RT)
- EPICS support

4.4 IOxOS ADC3110

The signals from the preamplifier are connected to an IOxOS ADC3110 FMC card. A circuit inside the FPGA is reading the samples at 50.0000MHz and processing one DDC channel for each ADC.

As the IFC1210 is supporting 8 DDC channels, an 8 channel ADC FMC card with 16bit resolution is the best fit for this application. The IOxOS AC3110 has been selected as this board is well supported for the IOxOS IFC1210 board.

The ADC3110 offers 4 dual channel 16bit ADCs operating at up to 250Msps. There is a local low-noise oscillator and PLL that allows the configuration of 50.0000Msps operation. The clock distribution has sufficient low jitter for under-sampling of the 101MHz signals and the ADC bandwidth is $\gg 100\text{MHz}$.

Each IFC1210 board is equipped with one ADC3110 populated in the FMC1 slot.

Key specifications:

- 8 ADCs
- 16bit resolution
- 10dBm maximum input power
- ~400MHz bandwidth
- Configured to 50.0000Msps (250Msps max)
- Low jitter clock distribution with local oscillator and PLL (<200fs jitter)

Figure 9 ADC3110 Architecture

4.5 Software Architecture

The implementation is based on the EPICS, Linux and TOSCA-II framework available for the IFC1210 carrier board.

Figure 10 Digital Processing Architecture

The DDC is configured to have a 10 samples IQ buffer for each of the 8 DDCs. The amplitude calculations are executed by a stand-alone Linux application called mestra. The processing is synchronized to the DDC data buffers by a 5kHz interrupt coming from the DDC. The data buffers are implemented as FPGA DPRAM where the CPU can access the data as 32-bit organized memory. Access to data and interrupt synchronization is implemented by the Linux PEV driver.

Data exchange to the outside world is during debugging done through EPICS. During normal operation the mestra application is using a shared memory located physically inside the DRAM. At boot-up EPICS for Linux is started on the dual core processor. By accessing the controller over the EPICS Channel Access protocol data is remotely exchanged with the mestra application through the shared memory.

4.6 Digital Down Converter (MESTRA)

Each digital down converter (DDC) is used to filter out one harmonics of interest. During the filter process the information of the amplitude and phase are maintained. The DDC implemented in an FPGA is calculating the so called IQ values – where the signal is represented in Cartesian coordinates. To get the amplitude a Cartesian to polar conversion is required on the CPU.

The DDC is designed to operate with 50.0000Msps input and the decimation is factor 1000. This results in an output signal with 50ksps. The -3dB bandwidth of the DDC filters is only 18kHz. Due to this fact most of the input noise power is filtered by the DDC, resulting in a huge improvement in signal to noise ratio.

The DDC has been implemented with highest possible resolution that fits into the FPGA area. This strategy has been selected to get good numerical precision at signals with low intensity.

4.6.1 Architecture

There are 8 identical DDC channels where each channel can be assigned to any of the ADCs. In this application one DDC is assigned to each of the 8 ADCs. This allows filtering out one spectral component per ADC input.

The local oscillator is set exactly $2 \times 0.6328\text{MHz}$ for filtering the 2nd harmonics. The frequency integrator is a 32-bit adder operating at 50.0000MHz . The frequency resolution is 11.6mHz .

The –sine and cosine signals are generated by the CORDIC algorithm. The resolution of these functions is 24-bit.

The mixer is implemented with a 24-bit multiplier.

The CIC decimation filter has a 25-bit output resolution, has 4-stages and is configured to a 250:1 decimation. The CIC has a sinc transfer function in the pass band.

The CFIR is a 23-tap compensating FIR filter with 32-bit resolution. It has an inverse sinc transfer function in the pass band and compensates for the CIC filter.

The FIR filter is a 23-tap 32-bit resolution FIR filter with low pass band ripple.

Figure 11 DDC Architecture – One out of 8 channels

4.6.2 Implementation

The DDC is implemented partly in Matlab/Simulink (with automatic Simulink to VHDL conversion) and partly in hand-coded VHDL code. The NCO (Numerical Oscillator) and the CIC are implemented with automatic code generation and the CFIR and FIR filters are hand-coded. The reason for this was to save FPGA area by utilizing time-multiplexing in the FIR filters.

Figure 12 CIC-CFIR-FIR Transfer Function (Matlab)

The implementation goal of the CIC-CFIR-FIR filter has been to get a flat pass band, approx. 18kHz -3dB bandwidth and a very high attenuation for the stop band.

Figure 13 Transfer Function at 2nd harmonics (measured)

The bandwidth has been verified by measuring the transfer function at the 2nd harmonics. It shows a near to perfectly flat pass band for $\pm 12\text{kHz}$ (0.01dB ripple). This allows the local oscillator to be $\pm 40\text{ppm}$ off nominal frequency.

4.7 CPU Signal Processing (MESTRA)

The first step in the signal processing on the CPU is to convert the Cartesian IQ values from the DDC (FPGA) to polar coordinates. This is done in floating point.

$$MAG = \sqrt{I^2 + Q^2}$$

To get an absolute current IST in uA a calibration is required. This is done by setting a variable called EICH.

There is further possible to add linear temperature compensation setting the EICHT variable to a non-zero value. The EICHT is typically a positive value to compensate for increased losses in the cables at increased temperature.

$$IST = MAG \cdot EICH \cdot (1 + EICHT \cdot EXT_TEMP0)$$

4.8 EPICS Interface

The EPICS (Experimental Physics and Industrial Control) define Ethernet for system-wide communication. The EPICS core is executed on the local P2020 CPU's. The EPICS interface is connected to "eth0".

<PRE> = "T-M" for Test Mode (operated in parallel to the CAMAC MESTRA/STRAM system)

<PRE> = "M" for Production Mode (replacing the CAMAC MESTRA/STRAM system)

| Channel | Description | Type | Units |
|----------------------------|--------------------------------------|--------|-----------|
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC Signals | | | |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK0 | ADC0 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK1 | ADC1 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK2 | ADC2 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK3 | ADC3 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK4 | ADC4 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK5 | ADC5 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK6 | ADC6 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK7 | ADC7 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG0 | DDC0 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG1 | DDC1 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG2 | DDC2 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG3 | DDC3 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG4 | DDC4 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG5 | DDC5 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG6 | DDC6 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG7 | DDC7 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP1:2 | External Temperature #1 | REAL64 | °C |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP2:2 | External Temperature #2 | REAL64 | °C |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP3:2 | External Temperature #3 | REAL64 | °C |
| ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP4:2 | External Temperature #4 | REAL64 | °C |
| MESTRA A | | | |
| <PRE>HC1:EICH:1 | MHC1 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>HC1:EICHT:1 | MHC1 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>HC1:INTL:2 | MHC1 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC1:IST:2 | MHC1 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC2:EICH:1 | MHC2 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>HC2:EICHT:1 | MHC2 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>HC2:INTL:2 | MHC2 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC2:IST:2 | MHC2 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>BC1:EICH:1 | MBC1 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>BC1:EICHT:1 | MBC1 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>BC1:INTL:2 | MBC1 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>BC1:IST:2 | MBC1 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>BC1B:EICH:1 | MBC1B Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>BC1B:EICHT:1 | MBC1B Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>BC1B:INTL:2 | MBC1B Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>BC1B:IST:2 | MBC1B Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC3:EICH:1 | MHC3 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>HC3:EICHT:1 | MHC3 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>HC3:INTL:2 | MHC3 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC3:IST:2 | MHC3 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC4:EICH:1 | MHC4 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |

| <PRE>HC4:EICHT:1 | MHC4 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
|---------------------|---|--------|-------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|----------------------------|--------|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|-------------------|---|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|--------------------|----|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|-------------------|--------|--|
| <PRE>HC4:INTL:2 | MHC4 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC4:IST:2 | MHC4 Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5:EICH:1 | MHC5 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5:EICHT:1 | MHC5 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5:INTL:2 | MHC5 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5:IST:2 | MHC5 Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC6:EICH:1 | MHC6 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC6:EICHT:1 | MHC6 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC6:INTL:2 | MHC6 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC6:IST:2 | MHC6 Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>H1H6:INHIBIT:2 | Inhibit Status
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>INHIBIT1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>INHIBIT2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>INHIBIT3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>INHIBIT4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | INHIBIT1 | 1 | INHIBIT2 | 2 | INHIBIT3 | 3 | INHIBIT4 | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | INHIBIT1 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | INHIBIT2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | INHIBIT3 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | INHIBIT4 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>H1H6:ISTA:2 | Interlock Status
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>MHC1:IST:2 > MHC1:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>MHC2:IST:2 > MHC2:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>MBC1:IST:2 > MBC1:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>MBC1B:IST:2 > MBC1B:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>MHC3:IST:2 > MHC3:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>MHC6:IST:2 > MHC6:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>MHC1:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>MHC2:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>MBC1:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11</td> <td>MBC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>MHC3:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>13</td> <td>MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14</td> <td>MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>15</td> <td>MHC6:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | MHC1:IST:2 > MHC1:INTL:2 | 1 | MHC2:IST:2 > MHC2:INTL:2 | 2 | MBC1:IST:2 > MBC1:INTL:2 | 3 | MBC1B:IST:2 > MBC1B:INTL:2 | 4 | MHC3:IST:2 > MHC3:INTL:2 | 5 | MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2 | 6 | MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2 | 7 | MHC6:IST:2 > MHC6:INTL:2 | 8 | MHC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 9 | MHC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 10 | MBC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 11 | MBC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 12 | MHC3:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 13 | MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 14 | MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 15 | MHC6:EICH:1 = 0.0 | UINT32 | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | MHC1:IST:2 > MHC1:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | MHC2:IST:2 > MHC2:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | MBC1:IST:2 > MBC1:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | MBC1B:IST:2 > MBC1B:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 4 | MHC3:IST:2 > MHC3:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 5 | MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 6 | MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 7 | MHC6:IST:2 > MHC6:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 8 | MHC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 9 | MHC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 10 | MBC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 11 | MBC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 12 | MHC3:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 13 | MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 14 | MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 15 | MHC6:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC1:IIST:2 | MHC1 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC2:IIST:2 | MHC2 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>BC1:IIST:2 | MBC1 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>BC1B:IIST:2 | MBC1B Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC3:IIST:2 | MHC3 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC4:IIST:2 | MHC4 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5:IIST:2 | MHC5 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC6:IIST:2 | MHC6 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>H1H6:IIST | Interlock Status at Interlock | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |

| | Bit | Description | | |
|--|--|-----------------------------|--------|--------|
| | 0 | MHC1:IST:2 > MHC1:INTL:2 | | |
| | 1 | MHC2:IST:2 > MHC2:INTL:2 | | |
| | 2 | MBC1:IST:2 > MBC1:INTL:2 | | |
| | 3 | MBC1B:IST:2 > MBC1B:INTL:2 | | |
| | 4 | MHC3:IST:2 > MHC3:INTL:2 | | |
| | 5 | MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2 | | |
| | 6 | MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2 | | |
| | 7 | MHC6:IST:2 > MHC6:INTL:2 | | |
| | 8 | MHC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 9 | MHC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 10 | MBC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 11 | MBC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 12 | MHC3:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 13 | MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 14 | MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 15 | MHC6:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| STRAM MHTR1 EHT Losses (MHC1, MHC2, MBC1) | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR1H1:TRWM:2 | MHC1 Current Filtered | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1H2:TRWM:2 | MHC2 Current Filtered | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1B1:TRWM:2 | MBC1 Current Filtered | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1:TRDI:2 | Current Losses | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1:ISTA:2 | Interlock Status | | UINT32 | |
| | Bit | Description | | |
| | 0 | MHC1 – MHC2 Losses too High | | |
| <PRE>HTR1H1:TIWM:2 | MHC1 Current Filtered at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1H2:TIWM:2 | MHC2 Current Filtered at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1B1:TIWM:2 | MBC1 Current Filtered at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1:TIDI:2 | Current Losses at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1:IIST:2 | Interlock Status at Interlock | | UINT32 | |
| | Bit | Description | | |
| | 0 | MHC1 – MHC2 Losses too High | | |
| <PRE>HTR1:SV:2 | Expected Splitter Losses MHC1*MBC1 (Scaling) | | REAL64 | 1/uA |
| <PRE>HTR1:MV:2 | Maximum Losses MHC1-(MHC2+MBC1) | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1:EV:2 | Maximum Losses at zero Current
Loss Max = (MV*MHC1/NCUR+EV) | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR1:FKI:2 | Integration Cycles (200us) for FIR Averaging Filter | | UINT32 | 200us |
| <PRE>HTR1:FK0:2 | Filter Time at zero Current (FK0*FKI*200us) | | REAL64 | cycles |
| <PRE>HTR1:FKE:2 | Filter Time Epsilon
Filter Time = (FK0-FK0*MHC1/NCUR+FKE)*FKI*200us | | REAL64 | cycles |
| <PRE>HTR1:NCUR:2 | Normalized Current | | REAL64 | uA |
| STRAM MHTR2 P-Channel Losses (MHC2, MHC3, MHC4, MHC5) | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H2:TRWM:2 | MHC2 Current Filtered | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR2H3:TRWM:2 | MHC3 Current Filtered | | REAL64 | uA |

| <PRE>HTR2H4:TRWM:2 | MHC4 Current Filtered | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
|--------------------------------------|---|--------|-------------|---|-----------------------------|---|-----------------------------|---|-----------------------------|---|----------------------------|--|--|
| <PRE>HTR2H5:TRWM:2 | MHC5 Current Filtered | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| PRE>HTR2M:TRTR:2 | Transmission MHC4/MHC3 | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | |
| PRE>HTR2E:TRTR:2 | Transmission MHC5/MHC4 | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:ISTA:2 | Interlock Status | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>MHC2 – MHC3 Losses too High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>MHC3 – MHC4 Losses too High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | MHC2 – MHC3 Losses too High | 1 | MHC3 – MHC4 Losses too High | 2 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High | 3 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | MHC2 – MHC3 Losses too High | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | MHC3 – MHC4 Losses too High | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H2:TIWM:2 | MHC2 Current Filtered at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H3:TIWM:2 | MHC3 Current Filtered at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H4:TIWM:2 | MHC4 Current Filtered at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H5:TIWM:2 | MHC5 Current Filtered at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| PRE>HTR2M:TITR:2 | Transmission MHC4/MHC3 at Interlock | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | |
| PRE>HTR2E:TITR:2 | Transmission MHC5/MHC4 at Interlock | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:IIST:2 | Interlock Status at Interlock | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>MHC2 – MHC3 Losses too High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>MHC3 – MHC4 Losses too High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | MHC2 – MHC3 Losses too High | 1 | MHC3 – MHC4 Losses too High | 2 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High | 3 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | MHC2 – MHC3 Losses too High | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | MHC3 – MHC4 Losses too High | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2M:SV:2 | Expected Losses MHC3-MHC4 | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2E:SV:2 | Expected Losses MHC4-MHC5 | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2E:SVI:2 | Expected Losses current dependent MHC4-MHC5 | REAL64 | %/uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:MV:2 | Maximum Losses MHC2-MHC3 | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:EV:2 | Maximum Losses at zero Current MHC2-MHC3
Loss Max = MV*MHC2/NCUR+EV | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2M:MV:2 | Maximum Losses MHC3-MHC4 | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2M:EV:2 | Maximum Losses at zero Current MHC3-MHC4
Loss Max = MV*MHC3/NCUR+EV | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2E:MV:2 | Maximum Losses MHC4-MHC5 | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2E:EV:2 | Maximum Losses at zero Current MHC4-MHC5
Loss Max = MV*MHC4/NCUR+EV | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:FKI:2 | Integration Cycles (200us) for FIR Averaging Filter | UINT32 | 200us | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:FK0:2 | Filter Time at zero Current (FK0*FKI*200us) | REAL64 | cycles | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:FKE:2 | Filter Time Epsilon
Filter Time = (FK0-FK0*MHC2/NCUR+FKE)*FKI*200us | REAL64 | cycles | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2:NCUR:2 | Normalized Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| STRAM MHTR3 SINQ Losses (MHC5, MHC6) | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR3H5:TRWM:2 | MHC5 Current Filtered | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR3H6:TRWM:2 | MHC6 Current Filtered | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:TRDI:2 | Current Losses | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:ISTA:2 | Interlock Status | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | |

| | Bit | | Description | | | |
|--------------------|--|---|-----------------------------|----------------------------|-----------------------------|----------------------------|
| | | | | | | |
| | 0 | 1 | MHC5 – MHC6 Losses too High | MHC5 – MHC6 Losses too Low | | |
| <PRE>HTR3H5:TIWM:2 | MHC5 Current Filtered at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA | | |
| <PRE>HTR3H6:TIWM:2 | MHC6 Current Filtered at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:TIDI:2 | Current Losses at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:IIST:2 | Interlock Status at Interlock | | UINT32 | | | |
| | Bit | | | | Description | |
| | 0 | 1 | | | MHC5 – MHC6 Losses too High | MHC5 – MHC6 Losses too Low |
| <PRE>HTR3:SV:2 | Expected Losses MHC5-MBC6 | | REAL64 | 1/uA | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:MV:2 | Maximum Losses MHC5-MHC6 | | REAL64 | uA | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:EV:2 | Maximum Losses at zero Current
Loss Max = (MV*MHC5/NCUR+EV) | | REAL64 | uA | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:FKI:2 | Integration Cycles (200us) for FIR Averaging Filter | | UINT32 | cycles | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:FK0:2 | Filter Time at zero Current (FK0*FKI*200us) | | REAL64 | cycles | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:FKE:2 | Filter Time Epsilon
Filter Time = (FK0-FK0*MHC5/NCUR+FKE)*FKI*200us | | REAL64 | cycles | | |
| <PRE>HTR3:NCUR:2 | Normalized Current | | REAL64 | uA | | |

Table 4 EPICS Interface Specifications ZPSAF66-VMEIFC Slot#1

| Channel | Description | Type | Units |
|----------------------------|--------------------------------------|--------|-----------|
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC Signals | | | |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK0 | ADC0 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK1 | ADC1 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK2 | ADC2 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK3 | ADC3 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK4 | ADC4 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK5 | ADC5 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK6 | ADC6 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK7 | ADC7 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG0 | DDC0 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG1 | DDC1 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG2 | DDC2 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG3 | DDC3 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG4 | DDC4 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG5 | DDC5 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG6 | DDC6 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG7 | DDC7 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP1:2 | External Temperature #1 | REAL64 | °C |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP2:2 | External Temperature #2 | REAL64 | °C |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP3:2 | External Temperature #3 | REAL64 | °C |
| ZPSAF67-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP4:2 | External Temperature #4 | REAL64 | °C |
| MESTRA B | | | |
| <PRE>XC1:EICH:1 | MXC1 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>XC1:EICHT:1 | MXC1 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>XC1:INTL:2 | MXC1 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>XC1:IST:2 | MXC1 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>XC2:EICH:1 | MXC2 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>XC2:EICHT:1 | MXC2 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>XC2:INTL:2 | MXC2 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>XC2:IST:2 | MXC2 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NC1:EICH:1 | MNC1 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>NC1:EICHT:1 | MNC1 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>NC1:INTL:2 | MNC1 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NC1:IST:2 | MNC1 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NC3:EICH:1 | MNC3 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>NC3:EICT:1 | MNC3 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>NC3:INTL:2 | MNC3 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NC3:IST:2 | MNC3 Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC1B:EICH:1 | MHC1B Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |
| <PRE>HC1B:EICHT:1 | MHC1B temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C |
| <PRE>HC1B:INTL:2 | MHC1B Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HC1B:IST:2 | MHC1B Current | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>YC1:EICH:1 | MYC1 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits |

| <PRE>YC1:EICHT:1 | MYC1 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
|---------------------|---|--------|-------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|--------|----------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------------------|---|--------------|---|-------------------|---|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|--------------------|----|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|--------------|--------|--|
| <PRE>YC1:INTL:2 | MYC1 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>YC1:IST:2 | MYC1 Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>YC2:EICH:1 | MYC2 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>YC2:EICHT:1 | MYC2 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>YC2:INTL:2 | MYC2 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>YC2:IST:2 | MYC2 Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>X1Y2:INHIBIT:2 | Interlock Status
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>INHIBIT1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>INHIBIT2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>INHIBIT3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>INHIBIT4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | INHIBIT1 | 1 | INHIBIT2 | 2 | INHIBIT3 | 3 | INHIBIT4 | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | INHIBIT1 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | INHIBIT2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | INHIBIT3 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | INHIBIT4 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>X1Y2:ISTA:2 | Interlock Status
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>MXC1:IST:2 > MXC1:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>MXC2:IST:2 > MXC2:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>MNC1:IST:2 > MNC1:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>MNC3:IST:2 > MNC3:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>MHC1B:IST:2 > MHC1B:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>MYC1:IST:2 > MYC1:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>MYC2:IST:2 > MYC2:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Reserved = 0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>MXC1:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>MXC2:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10</td> <td>MNC1:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11</td> <td>MNC3:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>12</td> <td>MHC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>13</td> <td>MYC1:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14</td> <td>MYC2:EICH:1 = 0.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>15</td> <td>Reserved = 0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | MXC1:IST:2 > MXC1:INTL:2 | 1 | MXC2:IST:2 > MXC2:INTL:2 | 2 | MNC1:IST:2 > MNC1:INTL:2 | 3 | MNC3:IST:2 > MNC3:INTL:2 | 4 | MHC1B:IST:2 > MHC1B:INTL:2 | 5 | MYC1:IST:2 > MYC1:INTL:2 | 6 | MYC2:IST:2 > MYC2:INTL:2 | 7 | Reserved = 0 | 8 | MXC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 9 | MXC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 10 | MNC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 11 | MNC3:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 12 | MHC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 13 | MYC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 14 | MYC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 15 | Reserved = 0 | UINT32 | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | MXC1:IST:2 > MXC1:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | MXC2:IST:2 > MXC2:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | MNC1:IST:2 > MNC1:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | MNC3:IST:2 > MNC3:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 4 | MHC1B:IST:2 > MHC1B:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 5 | MYC1:IST:2 > MYC1:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 6 | MYC2:IST:2 > MYC2:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 7 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 8 | MXC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 9 | MXC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 10 | MNC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 11 | MNC3:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 12 | MHC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 13 | MYC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 14 | MYC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 15 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>XC1:IIST:2 | MXC1 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>XC2:IIST:2 | MXC2 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>NC1:IIST:2 | MNC1 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>NC3:IIST:2 | MNC3 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC1B:IIST:2 | MHC1B Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>YC1:IIST:2 | MYC1 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>YC2:IIST:2 | MYC2 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>X1Y2:IIST | Interlock Status at Interlock
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>MXC1:IST:2 > MXC1:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>MXC2:IST:2 > MXC2:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>MNC1:IST:2 > MNC1:INTL:2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>MNC3:IST:2 > MNC3:INTL:2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | MXC1:IST:2 > MXC1:INTL:2 | 1 | MXC2:IST:2 > MXC2:INTL:2 | 2 | MNC1:IST:2 > MNC1:INTL:2 | 3 | MNC3:IST:2 > MNC3:INTL:2 | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | MXC1:IST:2 > MXC1:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | MXC2:IST:2 > MXC2:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | MNC1:IST:2 > MNC1:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | MNC3:IST:2 > MNC3:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |

| | | | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|-----------------------------|--------|--------|
| | 4 | MHC1B:IST:2 > MHC1B:INTL:2 | | |
| | 5 | MYC1:IST:2 > MYC1:INTL:2 | | |
| | 6 | MYC2:IST:2 > MYC2:INTL:2 | | |
| | 7 | Reserved = 0 | | |
| | 8 | MXC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 9 | MXC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 10 | MNC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 11 | MNC3:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 12 | MHC1B:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 13 | MYC1:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 14 | MYC2:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | |
| | 15 | Reserved = 0 | | |
| STRAM MNTR Ring Losses (MNC3, MHC1) | | | | |
| <PRE>NTRN3:TRWM:2 | MNC3 Current Filtered | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTRH1:TRWM:2 | MHC1 Current Filtered | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTR:TRDI:2 | Current Losses | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTR:ISTA:2 | Interlock Status | | UINT32 | |
| | Bit | Description | | |
| | 0 | MNC3 – MHC1 Losses too High | | |
| | 1 | MNC3 – MHC1 Losses too Low | | |
| <PRE>NTRN3:TIWM:2 | MNC3 Current Filtered at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTRH1:TIWM:2 | MHC1 Current Filtered at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTR:TIDI:2 | Current Losses at Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTR:IIST:2 | Interlock Status at Interlock | | UINT32 | |
| | Bit | Description | | |
| | 0 | MNC3 – MHC1 Losses too High | | |
| | 1 | MNC3 – MHC1 Losses too Low | | |
| <PRE>NTR:SV:2 | Expected Losses MNC3-MHC1 | | REAL64 | % |
| <PRE>NTR:MV:2 | Maximum Losses MNC3-MHC1 | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTR:EV:2 | Maximum Losses at zero Current
Loss Max = (MV*MNC3/NCUR+EV) | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>NTR:FKI:2 | Integration Cycles (200us) for FIR Averaging Filter | | UINT32 | cycles |
| <PRE>NTR:FK0:2 | Filter Time at zero Current (FK0*FKI*200us) | | REAL64 | cycles |
| <PRE>NTR:FKE:2 | Filter Time Epsilon
Filter Time = (FK0-FK0*MNC3/NCUR+FKE)*FKI*200us | | REAL64 | cycles |
| <PRE>NTR:NCUR:2 | Normalized Current | | REAL64 | uA |

Table 5 EPICS Interface Specifications ZPSAF67-VMEIFC Slot#2

| Channel | Description | Type | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | |
|----------------------------|---|--------|-------------|---|-------------------|---|-------------------|---|-------------------|---|--------------------|--------|--------------|--------|--|
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC Signals | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK0 | ADC0 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK1 | ADC1 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK2 | ADC2 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK3 | ADC3 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK4 | ADC4 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK5 | ADC5 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK6 | ADC6 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:ADC-PEAK7 | ADC7 Peak Value | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG0 | DDC0 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG1 | DDC1 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG2 | DDC2 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG3 | DDC3 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG4 | DDC4 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG5 | DDC5 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG6 | DDC6 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:DDC-MAG7 | DDC7 Magnitude | REAL64 | digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP1:2 | External Temperature #1 | REAL64 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP2:2 | External Temperature #2 | REAL64 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP3:2 | External Temperature #3 | REAL64 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| ZPSAF68-VMEIFC:EXT-TEMP4:2 | External Temperature #4 | REAL64 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| MESTRA C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC4-M:EICH:1 | MHC4 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC4-M:EICHT:1 | MHC4 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC4-M:INTL:2 | MHC4 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC4-M:IST:2 | MHC4 Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5-M:EICH:1 | MHC5 Current Calibration Factor | REAL64 | uA/digits | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5-M:EICHT:1 | MHC5 Temperature Calibration Factor | REAL64 | 1/°C | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5-M:INTL:2 | MHC5 Interlock Level | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5-M:IST:2 | MHC5 Current | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>H4H5-M:INHIBIT:2 | Inhibit Status <table border="1" style="width: 100%; margin-top: 5px;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>INHIBIT1 (unused)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>INHIBIT2 (unused)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>INHIBIT3 (unused)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>INHIBIT4 (MHTR2-M)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | INHIBIT1 (unused) | 1 | INHIBIT2 (unused) | 2 | INHIBIT3 (unused) | 3 | INHIBIT4 (MHTR2-M) | UINT32 | | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | INHIBIT1 (unused) | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | INHIBIT2 (unused) | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | INHIBIT3 (unused) | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | INHIBIT4 (MHTR2-M) | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>H4H5-M:ISTA:" | Interlock Status <table border="1" style="width: 100%; margin-top: 5px;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Reserved = 0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Reserved = 0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Reserved = 0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Reserved = 0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Reserved = 0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | Reserved = 0 | 1 | Reserved = 0 | 2 | Reserved = 0 | 3 | Reserved = 0 | 4 | Reserved = 0 | UINT32 | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 4 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |

| | <table border="1"> <tr><td>5</td><td>MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> </table> | 5 | MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2 | 6 | MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2 | 7 | Reserved = 0 | 8 | Reserved = 0 | 9 | Reserved = 0 | 10 | Reserved = 0 | 11 | Reserved = 0 | 12 | Reserved = 0 | 13 | MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 14 | MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 15 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
|--|--|--------|--------------------------|--------|-----------------------------|---|----------------------------|--------|--------------|---|--------------|----|--------------|----|--------------------------|----|--------------------------|----|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|--------------|----|--------------|----|--------------|----|--------------|----|-------------------|----|-------------------|----|--------------|--------|--|
| 5 | MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 6 | MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 7 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 8 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 9 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 10 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 11 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 12 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 13 | MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 14 | MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 15 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC4-M:IIST:2 | MHC4 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HC5-M:IIST:2 | MHC5 Current at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>H4H5-M:IIST:2 | Interlock Status at Interlock <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>0</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0</td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0</td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>Reserved = 0</td></tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | Reserved = 0 | 1 | Reserved = 0 | 2 | Reserved = 0 | 3 | Reserved = 0 | 4 | Reserved = 0 | 5 | MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2 | 6 | MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2 | 7 | Reserved = 0 | 8 | Reserved = 0 | 9 | Reserved = 0 | 10 | Reserved = 0 | 11 | Reserved = 0 | 12 | Reserved = 0 | 13 | MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 14 | MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0 | 15 | Reserved = 0 | UINT32 | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 2 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 3 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 4 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 5 | MHC4:IST:2 > MHC4:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 6 | MHC5:IST:2 > MHC5:INTL:2 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 7 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 8 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 9 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 10 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 11 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 12 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 13 | MHC4:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 14 | MHC5:EICH:1 = 0.0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 15 | Reserved = 0 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| STRAM MHR2-M MEGAPIE Losses (MHC4, MHC5) | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H4-M:TRWM:2 | MHC4 Current Filtered | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H5-M:TRWM:2 | MHC5 Current Filtered | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2E-M:TRTR:2 | Transmission MHC5/MHC4 | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2-M:ISTA:2 | Interlock Status <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>0</td><td>MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low</td></tr> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | 0 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High | 1 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 0 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| 1 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H4-M:TIWM:2 | MHC4 Current Filtered at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2H5-M:TIWM:2 | MHC5 Current Filtered at Interlock | REAL64 | uA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2E-M:TITR:2 | Transmission MHC5/MHC4 at Interlock | REAL64 | % | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| <PRE>HTR2-M:IIST:2 | Interlock Status at Interlock <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Bit</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> </tbody> </table> | Bit | Description | UINT32 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Bit | Description | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |

| | | | | |
|---------------------|--|-----------------------------|--------|--------|
| | 0 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too High | | |
| | 1 | MHC4 – MHC5 Losses too Low | | |
| <PRE>HTR2E-M:SV:2 | Expected Losses MHC4-MHC5 | | REAL64 | % |
| <PRE>HTR2E-M:SVI:2 | Expected Losses current dependent MHC4-MHC5 | | REAL64 | %/uA |
| <PRE>HTR2E-M:MV:2 | Maximum Losses MHC4-MHC5 | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR2E-M:EV:2 | Maximum Losses at zero Current MHC4-MHC5
Loss Max = MV*MHC4/NCUR+EV | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR2-M:FKI:2 | Integration Cycles (200us) for FIR Averaging Filter | | UINT32 | 200us |
| <PRE>HTR2-M:FK0:2 | Filter Time at zero Current (FK0*FKI*200us) | | REAL64 | cycles |
| <PRE>HTR2-M:FKE:2 | Filter Time Epsilon
Filter Time = (FK0-FK0*MHC2/NCUR+FKE)*FKI*200us | | REAL64 | cycles |
| <PRE>HTR2-M:NCUR:2 | Normalized Current | | REAL64 | uA |
| <PRE>HTR2-M:IIMIN:2 | Minimum Current for Interlock | | REAL64 | uA |

Table 6 EPICS Interface Specifications ZPSAF68-VMEIFC Slot#3

4.9 Interlock Interface

The Interlock Interface is compatible to the PSI HIPA interlock system. The interface is implemented with the PSI DIN-Rail Interlock Unit. If no error condition is detected, the IFC1210 controller sends a 2.5kHz binary signal to the EtherCAT EL2124 digital 5V output. The digital outputs of the EL2124 are connected to the DIN-Rail Interlock Units and deactivate the Interlock signals. There are EtherCAT EL1124 digital 5V inputs that inhibits the generation of the Interlock signals.

Interlock is activated when:

- Current monitors uninitialized
- Beam current above maximum limit
- Beam losses out of range
- Controller (IFC1210) is powered-down
- Controller (IFC1210) cyclic task stops
- EtherCAT I/O is powered-down
- EtherCAT I/O module failure (E-bus broken)
- Interlock Unit powered-down
- Broken EtherCAT wire

Figure 14 Interlock Implementation for one out of two slots

Several DIN-Rail Interlock Units are operated in parallel. If one DIN-Rail Interlock Unit malfunctions the VME MESTRA still trips the system.

4.9.1 Interlock Components

The interlock output signal is generated with a PSI specific device called DIN-Rail Interlock Unit. The enclosure is designed for being mounted on a DIN rail according to DIN EN 60715 TH 35. It uses the ERNI IDG-A enclosure.

Figure 15 Din-Rail Int

Figure 16 Din-Rail Interlock Unit Enclosure

The DIN-Rail Interlock Unit is designed to be attached to an EtherCAT 5V binary output module in 3-wire configuration (0V, +5V and TRIG). It supervises a toggling TRIG signal for failure. The supervisor consists of two retriggerable mono-flops, one triggered on rising edge and one on the falling edge of the TRIG signal. If it takes more than 500us without edges (falling or rising) interlock output signals INLK (LEMO PSI) and INTERLOCK (5V TTL – for debugging) are activated and a red LED is turned on. There is also a green power LED showing that the module has power.

Figure 17 Din-Rail Interlock Unit Block Diagram

Figure 18 Din-Rail Interlock Unit Layout

| Pin | Signal | Description | Level |
|-----------|-----------|-----------------------------------|-----------|
| J1-Left | Power | Power Supply | +5V |
| J1-Middle | Ground | Ground | GND |
| J1-Right | TRIG | 5V Trigger Signal | TTL - In |
| J2-Left | Power | Power Supply | +5V |
| J2-Middle | Ground | Ground | GND |
| J2-Right | INTERLOCK | 5V Interlock Output – active High | TTL – Out |
| J3-Left | Power | Power Supply | +5V |
| J3-Middle | Ground | Ground | GND |
| J3-Right | NC | No Connect | NC |
| J4-Left | Power | Power Supply | +5V |
| J4-Middle | Ground | Ground | GND |
| J4-Right | NC | No Connect | NC |

Table 7 Connector Specifications J1, J2, J3 and J4 – Type: IDG-A

Figure 19 INLK J5 (LEMO Front View – PCB vertical)

| Pin | Signal | Description |
|------|--------|-----------------------------------|
| J5-1 | NOK | Normally Open without Interlock |
| J5-2 | POWER | +15V Power Supply |
| J5-3 | OK | Normally Closed without Interlock |

Table 8 Connector Specifications J5 – Type: LEMO EPG.00.303.NLN

4.9.2 Interlocks Slot#1

NOTE: To avoid interlocks the monitor calibration parameters EICH have to be set to a non-zero value!

| Condition | Description | Inhibit.#1.1 | Inhibit#1.2 | Inhibit#1.3 | Inhibit#1.4 | INLK#1.1 | INLK#1.2 |
|----------------|-----------------------------------|--------------|-------------|-------------|-------------|----------|----------|
| MH1H6:ISTA > 0 | Current and Calibration Interlock | | | | | X | X |
| MHTR1:ISTA > 0 | Transmission Interlock | X | | | | X | X |
| MHTR2:ISTA > 0 | Transmission Interlock | | X | | | X | X |
| MHTR3:ISTA > 0 | Transmission Interlock | | | X | | X | X |

Table 9 Interlock Implementation EC1 Slot#1

4.9.3 Interlocks Slot#2

NOTE: To avoid interlocks the monitor calibration parameters EICH have to be set to a non-zero value!

| Condition | Description | Inhibit#2.1 | Inhibit#2.2 | Inhibit#2.3 | Inhibit#2.4 | INLK#2.1 | INLK#2.2 |
|----------------|-----------------------------------|-------------|-------------|-------------|-------------|----------|----------|
| MX1Y2:ISTA > 0 | Current and Calibration Interlock | | | | | X | X |
| MNTR:ISTA > 0 | Transmission Interlock | X | | | | X | X |

Table 10 Interlock Implementation EC2 Slot#2

4.9.4 Interlocks Slot#3

NOTE: To avoid interlocks the monitor calibration parameters EICH have to be set to a non-zero value!

| Condition | Description | Inhibit.#3.1 | Inhibit#3.1 | Inhibit#3.3 | Inhibit#3.4 | INLK#3.1 | INLK#3.2 |
|------------------|-----------------------------------|--------------|-------------|-------------|-------------|----------|----------|
| MH4H5:ISTA > 0 | Current and Calibration Interlock | | | | | X | X |
| MHTR2-M:ISTA > 0 | Transmission Interlock | | | | X | X | X |

Table 11 Interlock Implementation EC3 Slot#3

4.10 EtherCAT Interface

There is IO connected on an EtherCAT master at interface “eth1”. The EtherCAT Master is implemented with the IgH EtherCAT Master Stack version 1.5.2. Configuration of the bus is “low-level” in C-code and is static in nature. The connection of the stack is done to the cyclic “mestra” application.

EtherCAT is used for the voltage, frequency, interlock outputs and inhibit inputs. To keep the I/O easier maintainable the I/O is divided into several segments each with a separate bus coupler.

4.10.1 EtherCAT Components

The EtherCAT IO is implemented with standard Beckhoff components.

Figure 20 Beckhoff EK1100 | EtherCAT Coupler

Figure 21 Beckhoff EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction

Figure 22 Beckhoff EK1501 | EtherCAT Coupler with ID switch, fibre optic

Figure 23 Beckhoff EL2521 | 1-channel pulse train output terminal RS422

Figure 24 Beckhoff EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 bit

Figure 25 Beckhoff EL4112 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0.20mA, 16 bit

Figure 26 Beckhoff EL3314 | 4-channel thermocouple input terminal

Figure 27 Beckhoff EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V

Figure 28 Beckhoff EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC

Figure 29 Beckhoff EL1124 | 4-channel digital input terminal 5V DC

Hinweis: Bei nicht benutzten Kanälen den Jumper JP1 entfernen.
 Dadurch werden die Eingänge intern abgeschlossen.

Figure 30 LEG SU3-2 Signalumwandler RS422-TTL

4.10.2 EtherCAT Slot#1 – MESTRA A

Type A:
12x Voltage 0..10V (Debug)
4x Frequency
4x Temperature
3x Fibre Optics
4x Inhibit Input(TTL)
4x Interlock Output (TTL)

Figure 31 EtherCAT Topology MESTRA A

| Position | Slave # | Type | Description | E-Bus [mA] | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
|---------------|---------------------|--------|--|-------------|--|-------------|-------|-------|-----------|--|-----|--------|-----------|---------------------------------------|---|------|-----------|--------------------|---|----|-----------|--------------------|---|----|
| EC1 Local I/O | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P0 | 0 | EL1100 | EtherCAT coupler #0 | -2000 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P1 | 1 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Output1</td> <td>ADC#0 Debug (MHC1)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Output2</td> <td>ADC#1 Debug (MHC2)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | Output1 | ADC#0 Debug (MHC1) | 4 | V/mA | Output2 | ADC#1 Debug (MHC2) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output1 | ADC#0 Debug (MHC1) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output2 | ADC#1 Debug (MHC2) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P2 | 2 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Output1</td> <td>ADC#2 Debug (MBC1)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Output2</td> <td>ADC#3 Debug (MBC1B)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | Output1 | ADC#2 Debug (MBC1) | 4 | V/mA | Output2 | ADC#3 Debug (MBC1B) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output1 | ADC#2 Debug (MBC1) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output2 | ADC#3 Debug (MBC1B) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P3 | 3 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Output1</td> <td>ADC#4 Debug (MHC3)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Output2</td> <td>ADC#5 Debug (MHC4)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | Output1 | ADC#4 Debug (MHC3) | 4 | V/mA | Output2 | ADC#5 Debug (MHC4) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output1 | ADC#4 Debug (MHC3) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output2 | ADC#5 Debug (MHC4) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P4 | 4 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Output1</td> <td>ADC#6 Debug (MHC5)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Output2</td> <td>ADC#7 Debug (MHC6)</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | Output1 | ADC#6 Debug (MHC5) | 4 | V/mA | Output2 | ADC#7 Debug (MHC6) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output1 | ADC#6 Debug (MHC5) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output2 | ADC#7 Debug (MHC6) | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P5 | 5 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Output1</td> <td>MHC6</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Output2</td> <td>MHC4</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | Output1 | MHC6 | 4 | V/mA | Output2 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output1 | MHC6 | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output2 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P6 | 6 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Output1</td> <td>MBC1</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Output2</td> <td>MBC1B</td> <td>4</td> <td>V/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | Output1 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | Output2 | MBC1B | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output1 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Output2 | MBC1B | 4 | V/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P7 | 7 | EL3314 | 4-channel analog input thermocouple, 16bit | 190 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>+TC1/-TC1</td> <td>Ext.Temp#1.1 Temperature Comp. (North)</td> <td>1</td> <td>°C</td> </tr> <tr> <td>+TC2/-TC2</td> <td>Ext.Temp#1.2 Temperature Comp. (West)</td> <td>1</td> <td>°C</td> </tr> <tr> <td>+TC3/-TC3</td> <td>Ext.Temp#1.3 Spare</td> <td>1</td> <td>°C</td> </tr> <tr> <td>+TC4/-TC4</td> <td>Ext.Temp#1.4 Spare</td> <td>1</td> <td>°C</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | +TC1/-TC1 | Ext.Temp#1.1 Temperature Comp. (North) | 1 | °C | +TC2/-TC2 | Ext.Temp#1.2 Temperature Comp. (West) | 1 | °C | +TC3/-TC3 | Ext.Temp#1.3 Spare | 1 | °C | +TC4/-TC4 | Ext.Temp#1.4 Spare | 1 | °C |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | +TC1/-TC1 | | Ext.Temp#1.1 Temperature Comp. (North) | 1 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | +TC2/-TC2 | | Ext.Temp#1.2 Temperature Comp. (West) | 1 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| +TC3/-TC3 | Ext.Temp#1.3 Spare | 1 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| +TC4/-TC4 | Ext.Temp#1.4 Spare | 1 | °C | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P8 | 8 | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | 70
-2000 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P9 | 9 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>+A / -A</td> <td>MHC1</td> <td>100</td> <td>kHz/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | +A / -A | MHC1 | 100 | kHz/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| +A / -A | MHC1 | 100 | kHz/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P10 | 10 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>+A / -A</td> <td>MBC1</td> <td>100</td> <td>kHz/mA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | +A / -A | MBC1 | 100 | kHz/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| +A / -A | MBC1 | 100 | kHz/mA | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| EC1.P11 | 11 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Terminal</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Scale</th> <th>Units</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |
| | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | | |

| | | | | | | | |
|---|----|--------|---|------------------------------|---------------------|--------------|-------------|
| | | | +A / -A | MHC3 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC1.P12 | 12 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | | | | 280 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | +A / -A | MHC4 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC1.P13 | 13 | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | | | | 70
-2000 |
| EC1.P14 | 14 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #1.0 | | | | 350 |
| EC1.P15 | 20 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #1.1 | | | | 350 |
| EC1.P16 | 26 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #1.2 | | | | 350 |
| EC1.P17 | 32 | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | | 90 |
| EC1.P18 | 33 | EL1124 | 4-channel digital input terminal 5V DC | | | | 90 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Input1 | Interlock Inhibit#1.1 | 5 | V | |
| | | | Input2 | Interlock Inhibit#1.2 | 5 | V | |
| | | | Input3 | Interlock Inhibit#1.3 | 5 | V | |
| | | | Input4 | Interlock Inhibit#1.4 | 5 | V | |
| EC1.P19 | 34 | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | | | | 130 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | Interlock TRIG#1.1 (INLK1.1) | 5 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | Interlock TRIG#1.2 (INLK1.2) | 5 | V | |
| | | | Output3 | Spare | 5 | V | |
| | | | Output4 | Spare | 5 | V | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | |
| EC1.0 Remote Outputs Block #0 (?00m fibre), Location: WEHA E23.8 (LogCAM) | | | | | | | |
| EC1.0.P0 | 15 | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | | | | -2000 |
| EC1.0.P1 | 16 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| EC1.0.P2 | 17 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| EC1.0.P3 | 18 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC1.0.P4 | 19 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | |
| EC1.1 Remote Outputs Block #1 (?00m fibre), Location: WNHA NA2.13.49 (LogCAM) | | | | | | | |
| EC1.1.P0 | 21 | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #1 | | | | -2000 |

| | | | | | | | |
|---|----|--------|---|--------------------|---------------------|--------------|-------|
| EC1.1.P1 | 22 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| EC1.1.P2 | 23 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| EC1.1.P3 | 24 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC1.1.P4 | 25 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | |
| EC1.2 Remote Outputs Block #2 (?00m fibre), Location: WEHA E2.21 (LogCAM) | | | | | | | |
| EC1.2.P0 | 27 | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #2 | | | | -2000 |
| EC1.2.P1 | 28 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| EC1.2.P2 | 29 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 LogIV | Log(IST/uA)*0.4+1.0 | V | |
| EC1.2.P3 | 30 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC1.2.P4 | 31 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MBC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | |

Table 12 EtherCAT Specifications Slot#1

4.10.3 EtherCAT Slot#2 – MESTRA B

Figure 32 EtherCAT Topology MESTRA B

| Position | Slave # | Type | Description | E-Bus [mA] | | | |
|---------------|---------|--------|---|---------------------|--|--------------|--------------|
| EC2 Local I/O | | | | | | | |
| EC2.P0 | 0 | EL1100 | EtherCAT coupler #0 | -2000 | | | |
| EC2.P1 | 1 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#0 Debug (MXC1) | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#1 Debug (MXC2) | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.P2 | 2 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#2 Debug (MNC1) | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#3 Debug (MNC3) | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.P3 | 3 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#4 Debug (MHC1B) | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#5 Debug (MYC1) | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.P4 | 4 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#6 Debug (MYC2) | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#7 Debug (Spare) | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC1.P5 | 5 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | MXC1 | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | MXC2 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC1.P6 | 6 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | MYC1 | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | MYC2 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.P7 | 7 | EL3314 | 4-channel analog input thermocouple, 16bit | 190 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | +TC1/-TC1 | | Ext.Temp#2.1 Temperature Comp. (Spare) | 1 | °C |
| | | | +TC2/-TC2 | | Ext.Temp#2.2 Temperature Comp. (Spare) | 1 | °C |
| | | | +TC3/-TC3 | | Ext.Temp#2.3 Spare | 1 | °C |
| | | | +TC4/-TC4 | Ext.Temp#2.4 Spare | 1 | °C | |
| EC1.P8 | 8 | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | 70
-2000 | | | |
| EC1.P9 | 9 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | +A / -A | MXC1 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC1.P10 | 10 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | +A / -A | MXC1 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC1.P11 | 11 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |

| | | | | | | | |
|--|----|--------|---|------------------------------|--------------|--------------|-------------|
| | | | +A / -A | MXC2 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC1.P12 | 12 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | | | | 280 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | +A / -A | MXC2 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC2.P13 | 13 | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | | | | 70
-2000 |
| EC2.P14 | 14 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #2.0 | | | | 350 |
| EC2.P15 | 20 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #2.1 | | | | 350 |
| EC2.P16 | 26 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #2.2 | | | | 350 |
| EC2.P17 | 27 | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | | 90 |
| EC2.P18 | 28 | EL1124 | 4-channel digital input terminal 5V DC | | | | 90 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Input1 | Interlock Inhibit#2.1 | 5 | V | |
| | | | Input2 | Interlock Inhibit#2.2 | 5 | V | |
| | | | Input3 | Interlock Inhibit#2.3 | 5 | V | |
| | | | Input4 | Interlock Inhibit#2.4 | 5 | V | |
| EC2.P19 | 29 | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | | | | 130 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | Interlock TRIG#2.1 (INLK2.1) | 5 | V | |
| | | | Output2 | Interlock TRIG#2.2 (INLK2.2) | 5 | V | |
| | | | Output3 | Spare | 5 | V | |
| | | | Output4 | Spare | 5 | V | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | |
| EC2.0 Remote Outputs Block #0, Location: WIHA/EG, G48.1 (RF) | | | | | | | |
| EC2.0.P0 | 15 | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | | | | -2000 |
| EC2.0.P1 | 16 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MXC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MXC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.0.P2 | 17 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MXC1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MCX1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.0.P3 | 18 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MCX1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MCX1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.0.P4 | 19 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MCX1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MCX1 | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | |
| EC2.1 Remote Outputs Block #1, Location: WSGA/OG S87.13 (RF) | | | | | | | |
| EC2.1.P0 | 21 | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #1 | | | | -2000 |

| | | | | | | | |
|----------|----|--------|---|--------------------|--------------|--------------|-----|
| EC2.1.P1 | 22 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.1.P2 | 23 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.1.P3 | 24 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC2.1.P4 | 25 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | | | | 210 |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | |
| | | | Output1 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | | Output2 | MHC1B | 4 | V/mA | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | |

Table 13 EtherCAT Specifications Slot#2

4.10.4 EtherCAT Slot#3 – MESTRA C

Figure 33 EtherCAT Topology MESTRA C

| Position | Slave # | Type | Description | E-Bus [mA] | | | |
|---------------|---------|--------|---|---------------------|--|--------------|--------------|
| EC1 Local I/O | | | | | | | |
| EC3.P0 | 0 | EL1100 | EtherCAT coupler #0 | -2000 | | | |
| EC3.P1 | 1 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#0 Debug - Spare | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#1 Debug - Spare | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC3.P2 | 2 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#2 Debug - Spare | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#3 Debug - Spare | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC3.P3 | 3 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#4 Debug - Spare | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#5 Debug (MHC4) | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC3.P4 | 4 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | ADC#6 Debug (MHC5) | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | ADC#7 Debug - Spare | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC3.P5 | 5 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | MHC4 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC3.P6 | 6 | EL4102 | 2-channel analog output terminal 0..10V, 16 Bit | 210 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | Output1 | | MHC5 | 4 | V/mA |
| | | | Output2 | MHC5 | 4 | V/mA | |
| EC3.P7 | 7 | EL3314 | 4-channel analog input thermocouple, 16bit | 190 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | +TC1/-TC1 | | Ext.Temp#1.1 Temperature Comp. (North) | 1 | °C |
| | | | +TC2/-TC2 | | Ext.Temp#1.2 Temperature Comp. (West) | 1 | °C |
| | | | +TC3/-TC3 | | Ext.Temp#1.3 Spare | 1 | °C |
| | | | +TC4/-TC4 | Ext.Temp#1.4 Spare | 1 | °C | |
| EC3.P8 | 8 | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | 70
-2000 | | | |
| EC3.P9 | 9 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | +A / -A | MHC4 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC3.P10 | 10 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |
| | | | +A / -A | MHC4 | 100 | kHz/mA | |
| EC3.P11 | 11 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | 280 | | | |
| | | | Terminal | | Description | Scale | Units |

| | | | | | | | | |
|---------|----|--------|--|------------------------------|--------------|--------------|-------------|--|
| | | | +A / -A | MHC5 | 100 | kHz/mA | | |
| EC3.P12 | 12 | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | | | | 280 | |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | | |
| | | | +A / -A | MHC5 | 100 | kHz/mA | | |
| EC3.P13 | 13 | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | | | | 70
-2000 | |
| EC3.P14 | 14 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #1.0 (no connect) | | | | 350 | |
| EC3.P15 | 15 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #1.1 (no connect) | | | | 350 | |
| EC3.P16 | 16 | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction #1.2 (no connect) | | | | 350 | |
| EC3.P17 | 17 | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | | 90 | |
| EC3.P18 | 18 | EL1124 | 4-channel digital input terminal 5V DC | | | | 90 | |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | | |
| | | | Input1 | Interlock Inhibit#1.1 | 5 | V | | |
| | | | Input2 | Interlock Inhibit#1.2 | 5 | V | | |
| | | | Input3 | Interlock Inhibit#1.3 | 5 | V | | |
| | | | Input4 | Interlock Inhibit#1.4 | 5 | V | | |
| EC3.P19 | 19 | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | | | | 130 | |
| | | | Terminal | Description | Scale | Units | | |
| | | | Output1 | Interlock TRIG#1.1 (INLK1.1) | 5 | V | | |
| | | | Output2 | Interlock TRIG#1.2 (INLK1.2) | 5 | V | | |
| | | | Output3 | Spare | 5 | V | | |
| | | | Output4 | Spare | 5 | V | | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | | |

Table 14 EtherCAT Specifications Slot#3

4.10.5 EtherCAT Slot#4 – MESTRA D

Figure 34 EtherCAT Topology MESTRA D

| Location | Type | Module | Module Name | I/O | Signal | Slave# | Delay | | |
|----------------|---|--------|---|----------|---|--------|----------|---|---|
| WBGA
B11.12 | A | EK1100 | EtherCAT coupler | | | 0 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM0 | EtherCAT | 1 | 1 | | |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 94 | 0.4 | | |
| | | EL1124 | 4-channel digital input terminal 5V DC | Input 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 95 | 0.4 | | |
| | | | | Input 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 | | |
| | | | | Input 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 | | |
| | | | | Input 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 | | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 | | |
| E5.10
(EXP) | B | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3 | EtherCAT | 2 | 2 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.0 | EtherCAT | 3 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.1 | EtherCAT | 11 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.2 | EtherCAT | 19 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.3 | EtherCAT | 27 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.4 | EtherCAT | 35 | 1 | | |
| | | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | | | 43 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.5 | EtherCAT | 44 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.6 | EtherCAT | 52 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.7 | EtherCAT | 60 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.8 | EtherCAT | 68 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.9 | EtherCAT | 76 | 1 | | |
| | | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | | | 84 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.10 | EtherCAT | 85 | 1 | | |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM3.11 | EtherCAT | 93 | 1 | | |
| | | | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| | | EXP3.0 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.0 | EtherCAT | 4 | 2 |
| EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | | | +A / -A | MHC1 | 5 | 0.4 | | |
| EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | | | +A / -A | MBC1 | 6 | 0.4 | | |
| EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | | | +A / -A | MHC3 | 7 | 0.4 | | |
| EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | | | +A / -A | MHC4 | 8 | 0.4 | | |
| EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | | | 9 | 0.4 | | |
| EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | | | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 10 | 0.4 | | |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 | | |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 | | |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 | | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 | | |
| EXP3.1 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.1 | EtherCAT | 12 | 2 | | |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 13 | 0.4 | | |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 14 | 0.4 | | |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 15 | 0.4 | | |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 16 | 0.4 | | |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 17 | 0.4 | | |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 18 | 0.4 | | |

| | | | | | | | |
|--------|---|--------|---|----------|---------------|----|-----|
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.2 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.2 | EtherCAT | 20 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 21 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 22 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 23 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 24 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 25 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 26 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.3 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3,3 | EtherCAT | 28 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 29 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 30 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 31 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 32 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 33 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 34 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.4 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.4 | EtherCAT | 36 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 37 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 38 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 39 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 40 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 41 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 42 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.5 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.5 | EtherCAT | 45 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 46 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 47 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 48 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 49 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 50 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 51 | 0.4 |

| | | | | | | | |
|--------|---|--------|---|----------|---------------|----|-----|
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.6 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.6 | EtherCAT | 53 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 54 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 55 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 56 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 57 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 58 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 59 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.7 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.7 | EtherCAT | 61 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 62 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 63 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 64 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 65 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 66 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 67 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.8 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.8 | EtherCAT | 69 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 70 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 71 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 72 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 73 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 74 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 75 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.9 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.9 | EtherCAT | 77 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 78 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 79 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 80 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 81 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 82 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 83 | 0.4 |

| | | | | | | | |
|---------|---|--------|---|----------|---------------|--------------|-------------|
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP3.10 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM3.10 | EtherCAT | 86 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 87 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 88 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 89 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 90 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 91 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 92 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| | | | | | | Sum Delay us | 67.2 |

Table 15 EtherCAT Specifications MESTRA D

All fibre cables 100m equal 1us added delay (duplex).

| Type | Units | EK1100 | EL9510 | EK1521 | EL9505 | EL1124 | EL2124 | EL9011 | EK1501 | EL2521 |
|------|--------|----------|----------|-----------|-----------|----------|-----------|-----------|-----------|-----------|
| A | 1 | 1 | 0 | 1 | 1 | 1 | 0 | 1 | 0 | 0 |
| B | 1 | 0 | 2 | 12 | 0 | 0 | 0 | 1 | 1 | 0 |
| C | 11 | 0 | 0 | 0 | 11 | 0 | 11 | 11 | 11 | 44 |
| | Total: | 1 | 2 | 13 | 12 | 1 | 11 | 13 | 12 | 44 |

Table 16 EtherCAT Components MESTRA D

4.10.6 EtherCAT Slot#5 – MESTRA E

Figure 35 EtherCAT Topology MESTRA E

| Location | Type | Module | Module Name | I/O | Signal | Slave# | Delay |
|-----------------|------|----------|---|----------|---------------|--------|-------|
| WBGA
B11.12 | A | EK1100 | EtherCAT coupler | | | 0 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4 | EtherCAT | 1 | 1 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 61 | 0.4 |
| | | EL1124 | 4-channel digital input terminal 5V DC | Input 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 62 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Input 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Input 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Input 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| E23.18
(EXP) | B | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4 | EtherCAT | 2 | 2 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.0 | EtherCAT | 3 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.1 | EtherCAT | 11 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.2 | EtherCAT | 19 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.3 | EtherCAT | 27 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.4 | EtherCAT | 35 | 1 |
| | | EL9410 | Power supply terminals for E-bus - 2A | | | 43 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.5 | EtherCAT | 44 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.6 | EtherCAT | 52 | 1 |
| | | EK1521 | 1-port EtherCAT fibre optic junction | MM4.7 | EtherCAT | 60 | 1 |
| | | | | EL9011 | End Cap | | |
| EXP4.0 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4.0 | EtherCAT | 4 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 5 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 6 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 7 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 8 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 9 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 10 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 | | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP4.1 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4.1 | EtherCAT | 12 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 13 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 14 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 15 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 16 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 17 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 18 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 | | |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP4.2 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4.2 | EtherCAT | 20 | 2 |

| | | | | | | | |
|--------|---|--------|---|----------|---------------|----|-----|
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 21 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 22 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 23 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 24 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 25 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 26 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP4.3 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4.3 | EtherCAT | 28 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 29 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 30 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 31 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 32 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 33 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 34 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP4.4 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4.4 | EtherCAT | 36 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 37 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 38 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 39 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 40 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 41 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 42 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP4.5 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4.5 | EtherCAT | 45 | 2 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 46 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 47 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 48 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 49 | 0.4 |
| | | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 50 | 0.4 |
| | | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 51 | 0.4 |
| | | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| EXP4.6 | C | EK1501 | Fibre Optical EtherCAT coupler Switch ID #0 | MM4.6 | EtherCAT | 53 | 2 |

| | | | | | | |
|--|--------|---|----------|---------------|--------------|-------------|
| | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC1 | 54 | 0.4 |
| | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MBC1 | 55 | 0.4 |
| | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC3 | 56 | 0.4 |
| | EL2521 | Pulse train output RS422 | +A / -A | MHC4 | 57 | 0.4 |
| | EL9505 | Power supply terminal 5V | | | 58 | 0.4 |
| | EL2124 | 4-channel digital output terminal 5V DC | Output 1 | B0 (UCN Kick) | 59 | 0.4 |
| | | | Output 2 | B1 (UCN WWK) | | 0 |
| | | | Output 3 | B2 (UCN WK) | | 0 |
| | | | Output 4 | B3 (Spare) | | 0 |
| | EL9011 | End Cap | | | | 0 |
| | | | | | Sum Delay us | 44.6 |

Table 17 EtherCAT Specifications MESTRA E

All fibre cables 100m equal 1us added delay (duplex).

| Type | Units | EK1100 | EL9510 | EK1521 | EL9505 | EL1124 | EL2124 | EL9011 | EK1501 | EL2521 |
|------|--------|----------|----------|----------|----------|----------|----------|----------|----------|-----------|
| A | 1 | 1 | 0 | 1 | 1 | 1 | 0 | 1 | 0 | 0 |
| B | 1 | 0 | 2 | 8 | 0 | 0 | 0 | 1 | 1 | 0 |
| C | 7 | 0 | 0 | 0 | 7 | 0 | 7 | 7 | 8 | 28 |
| | Total: | 1 | 2 | 9 | 8 | 1 | 7 | 9 | 9 | 28 |

Table 18 EtherCAT Components MESTRA E

4.11 Transmission Calculations (STRAM)

The transmission calculations are checking if the beam current losses are inside configurable limits. If the losses are too high or too low the transmission sub-system activates interlock output signals. This protects the HIPA machine from destruction if the beam gets “lost”.

There are five groups of transmission calculations – 4 executed on the slot#1 controller and 1 executed on the slot#2 controllers. The calculations are similar for all groups, but differ in algorithm according to the topology of the machine. The algorithms are based on the CAMAC STRAM implementations and are functional equivalents.

4.11.1 Transmissions Slot#1

STRAM assembler files used for defining slot#1 transmissions:

| ASM-File | Currents | EPICS Name |
|---------------|---------------------|------------|
| TRANSUCN.ASM: | MHC1,MBC1,MHC2 | MHTR1 |
| TRANS2H5.ASM: | MHC2,MHC3,MHC4,MHC5 | MHTR2 |
| TRANS5H6.ASM: | MHC5,MHC6 | MHTR3 |

4.11.1.1 TRANSUCN.ASM (MHTR1)

Description of assembler code in “quasi” code (not bit accurate).

```
// Outputs
MHC1      [uA]      // Digitized MHC1 current from MESTRA
MHC2      [uA]      // Digitized MHC2 current from MESTRA
MBC1      [uA]      // Digitized MBC1 current from MESTRA
LOSS12    [uA]      // Calculated losses (MHC1-(MHC2+MBC1))
INTL      [bit set] // Transmission, ++
MHC1_INTL [uA]      // MHC1 current at interlock
MHC2_INTL [uA]      // MHC2 current at interlock
MBC1_INTL [uA]      // MBC1 current at interlock
LOSS12_INTL [uA]    // Losses at interlock
INTL_INTL [bit set] // Interlock at interlock

// Inputs
SV12      [1/uA]    // Splitter losses MHC1*MBC1
DIFF1     [uA]      // Maximum difference
EPS1      [uA]      // Maximum loss at zero current
INT_N     [cycles]  // Integration time before processing
FILTCOEF  [cycles]  // Filter coefficient
FILTCOEFEPS [cycles] // Epsilon of filter coefficient
NORMCURR  [uA]      // Normalized current for difference

// Integration
if (INT_N < 1) {INT_N = 1}
// Accumulate over INT_N samples
if ( INT_COUNT < INT_N) {
    INT_COUNT = INT_COUNT + 1
    ACC_MHC1 = ACC_MHC1 + MHC1_IN
    ACC_MHC2 = ACC_MHC2 + MHC2_IN
```

```
        ACC_MBC1 = ACC_MBC1 + MHB1_IN
    } else {
// Calculate mean values over INT_N samples
    INT_COUNT = 0
    MEAN_MHC1 = ACC_MHC1 / INT_N
    MEAN_MHC2 = ACC_MHC2 / INT_N
    MEAN_MBC1 = ACC_MBC1 / INT_N
    ACC_MHC1 = 0
    ACC_MHC2 = 0
    ACC_MBC1 = 0
// Calculate filter coefficient
    if (MEAN_MHC1 > OLDREFCURR) {OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC1}
    EFFILCOEF=FILTCOEF * (1 - OLDREFCURR/NORMCURR) + FILTCOEFEPS
// Compensate stored filter sum for new filter coefficient
    K1 = OLDEFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K1 <= 1.0) {K1 = 1.0}
    K2 = EFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K2 <= 1.0) {
        K2 = 1.0
        EFFILCOEF = 2.0
    }
// Store old state for next calculation
    OLDEFFILCOEF = EFFILCOEF
    OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC1
// Calculate digital filter for MHC1
    DF_SUM_MHC1 = DF_SUM_MHC1 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC1 = DF_SUM_MHC1 + MEAN_MHC1
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC1 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC1 = DF_SUM_MHC1 - OUT
    MHC1 = OUT
// Calculate digital filter for MHC2
    DF_SUM_MHC2 = DF_SUM_MHC2 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC2 = DF_SUM_MHC2 + MEAN_MHC2
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC2 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC2 = DF_SUM_MHC2 - OUT
    MHC2 = OUT
// Calculate digital filter for MBC1
    DF_SUM_MBC1 = DF_SUM_MBC1 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MBC1 = DF_SUM_MBC1 + MEAN_MBC1
    OUT = DF_SUM_MBC1 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MBC1 = DF_SUM_MBC1 - OUT
    MBC1 = OUT
// Calculate losses
    LOSS = MHC1 - (MHC2 + MBC1)
    if (LOSS < 0.0) {LOSS12 = 0.0} else {LOSS12 = LOSS}
    MAX_LOSS = EPS1 + DIFF1 * MHC1 / NORMCURR
// Correct for splitter losses
    EFF_LOSS = MHC1 - (MHC2 + MBC1) - SV12 * MBC1 * MHC1 / 16000
    if (EFF_LOSS < 0.0) {EFF_LOSS = 0.0}
```

```

// Check if losses are within limit
    if (EFF_LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B12 = 1      }
// First interlock and timer logic
    if (INTL = 1 and timer == 0) {
// Start the timer
        timer = 1
/
// Copy interlock state
    MHC1_INTL = MHC1
    MHC2_INTL = MHC2
    MBC1_INTL = MBC1
    LOSS12_INTL = LOSS12
    INTL_INTL = INTL
    } elseif (timer > TIMEOUT_65MS) {
// Reset timer, interlock output and digital filter at beam ramp-down
    timer = 0
    INTL.B12 = 0
    DF_SUM_MHC1 = 0
    DF_SUM_MHC2 = 0
    DF_SUM_MBC1 = 0
    } else {
// Do nothing during 65ms
    timer = timer + 1
    }
}

```

4.11.1.2 TRANS2H5.ASM (MHTR2)

```

// Outputs
MHC2      [uA]      // Digitized MHC2 current from MESTRA
MHC3      [uA]      // Digitized MHC3 current from MESTRA
MHC4      [uA]      // Digitized MBC4 current from MESTRA
MHC5      [uA]      // Digitized MBC5 current from MESTRA
TRANS34   [0/00]    // Calculated transmission MHC4/MHC3
TRANS45   [0/00]    // Calculated transmission MHC5/MHC4
INTL      [bit set] // Transmission, ++
MHC2_INTL [uA]      // MHC2 current at interlock
MHC3_INTL [uA]      // MHC3 current at interlock
MHC4_INTL [uA]      // MHC4 current at interlock
MHC5_INTL [uA]      // MHC5 current at interlock
TRANS34_INTL [0/00] // Transmission MHC4/MHC3 at interlock
TRANS45_INTL [0/00] // Transmission MHC5/MHC4 at interlock
INTL_INTL [bit set] // Interlock at interlock

// Inputs
SV34      [0/00]    // Expected losses MHC3-4
SV45      [0/00]    // Expected losses MHC4-5
SVI45     [0/00/uA] // Expected losses current dep. MHC4-5
DIFF2     [uA]      // Maximum losses MHC2-MHC3

```

```
EPS2          [uA]      // Maximum loss at zero current
DIFF3         [uA]      // Maximum losses MHC3-MHC4
EPS3          [uA]      // Maximum loss at zero current
DIFF4         [uA]      // Maximum losses MHC4-MHC5
EPS4          [uA]      // Maximum loss at zero current
INT_N         [cycles] // Integration time before processing
FILTCOEFF     [cycles] // Filter coefficient
FILTCOEFEPS  [cycles] // Epsilon of filter coefficient
NORMCURR      [uA]      // Normalized current for difference

// Integration
  if (INT_N < 1) {INT_N = 1}
// Accumulate over INT_N samples
  if ( INT_COUNT < INT_N) {
    INT_COUNT = INT_COUNT + 1
    ACC_MHC2 = ACC_MHC2 + MHC2_IN
    ACC_MHC3 = ACC_MHC3 + MHC3_IN
    ACC_MHC4 = ACC_MHC4 + MHC4_IN
    ACC_MHC5 = ACC_MHC5 + MHC5_IN
  } else {
// Calculate mean values over INT_N samples
    INT_COUNT = 0
    MEAN_MHC2 = ACC_MHC2 / INT_N
    MEAN_MHC3 = ACC_MHC3 / INT_N
    MEAN_MHC4 = ACC_MHC4 / INT_N
    MEAN_MHC5 = ACC_MHC5 / INT_N
    ACC_MHC2 = 0
    ACC_MHC3 = 0
    ACC_MHC4 = 0
    ACC_MHC5 = 0
// Calculate filter coefficient
    if (MEAN_MHC2 > OLDREFCURR) {OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC2}
    EFFILCOEF = FILTCOEFF * (1 - OLDREFCURR/NORMCURR) + FILTCOEFEPS
// Compensate stored filter sum for new filter coefficient
    K1 = OLDEFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K1 <= 1.0) {K1 = 1.0}
    K2 = EFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K2 <= 1.0) {
      K2 = 1.0
      EFFILCOEF = 2.0
    }
// Store old state for next calculation
    OLDEFFILCOEF = EFFILCOEF
    OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC2
// Calculate digital filter for MHC2
    DF_SUM_MHC2 = DF_SUM_MHC2 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC2 = DF_SUM_MHC2 + MEAN_MHC2
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC2 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC2 = DF_SUM_MHC2 - OUT
    MHC2 = OUT
```

```
// Calculate digital filter for MHC3
  DF_SUM_MHC3 = DF_SUM_MHC3 / K1 * K2
  DF_SUM_MHC3 = DF_SUM_MHC3 + MEAN_MHC3
  OUT = DF_SUM_MHC3 / EFFILCOEF
  DF_SUM_MHC3 = DF_SUM_MHC3 - OUT
  MHC3 = OUT

// Calculate digital filter for MHC4
  DF_SUM_MHC4 = DF_SUM_MHC4 / K1 * K2
  DF_SUM_MHC4 = DF_SUM_MHC4 + MEAN_MHC4
  OUT = DF_SUM_MHC4 / EFFILCOEF
  DF_SUM_MHC4 = DF_SUM_MHC4 - OUT
  MHC4 = OUT

// Calculate digital filter for MHC5
  DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 / K1 * K2
  DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 + MEAN_MHC5
  OUT = DF_SUM_MHC5 / EFFILCOEF
  DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 - OUT
  MHC5 = OUT

// Calculate losses MHC2-MHC3
  MAX_LOSS = EPS2 + DIFF2 * MHC2 / NORMCURR
  LOSS = MHC2 - MHC3
  if (LOSS < 0.0) {LOSS2 = 0.0} else {LOSS2 = LOSS}

// Check if losses are within limit
  if (LOSS2 > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B23 = 1 } else {INTL.B23 = 0}

// Calculate losses MHC3-MHC4
  MAX_LOSS = EPS3 + DIFF3 * MHC3 / NORMCURR
  LOSS = (1000.0 - SV34) * MHC3 / 1000.0 - MHC4
  if (LOSS < 0.0) {LOSS3 = 0.0} else {LOSS3 = LOSS}

// Check if losses are within limit
  if (LOSS3 > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B34 = 1 } else {INTL.B34 = 0}

// Calculate transmission MHC4/MHC3
  if (MHC3 < 1.0) {
    TRANS34 = 0.0
  } else {
    TRANS34 = MHC4 * 1000.0 / MHC3
  }

// Calculate losses MHC4-MHC5
  MAX_LOSS = EPS4 + DIFF4 * MHC4 / NORMCURR
  LOSS = MHC4 * (1000.0 - SV45 - (MHC4 * SVI45 / 1600)) / 1000.0
    - MHC5
  if (LOSS >= 0.0) {
    if (LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B45 = 1 }
  } else {
    if (-LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B45N = 1}
  }

// Calculate transmission MHC5/MHC4
  if (MHC4 < 1.0) {
    TRANS45 = 0.0
  } else {
```

```

        TRANS45 = MHC5 * 1000.0 / MHC4
    }
// First interlock and timer logic
    if (INTL and timer == 0) {
// Start the timer
        timer = 1
// Copy interlock state
        MHC2_INTL = MHC2
        MHC3_INTL = MHC3
        MHC4_INTL = MHC4
        MHC5_INTL = MHC5
        TRANS34_INTL = TRANS34
        TRANS45_INTL = TRANS45
// Set interlock output
        INTL.TRANS12 = 1
    } elseif (timer > TIMEOUT_65MS) {
// Reset timer, interlock output and digital filter at beam ramp-down
        timer = 0
        INTL.B23 = 0
        INTL.B34 = 0
        INTL.B45 = 0
        INTL.B45N = 0
        DF_SUM_MHC2 = 0
        DF_SUM_MHC3 = 0
        DF_SUM_MHC4 = 0
        DF_SUM_MHC5 = 0
    } else {
// Do nothing during 65ms
        timer = timer + 1
    }
}

```

4.11.1.3 TRANS5H6.ASM (MHTR3)

```

// Outputs
MHC5          [uA]      // Digitized MHC5 current from MESTRA
MHC6          [uA]      // Digitized MHC6 current from MESTRA
LOSS56        [uA]      // Calculated losses (MHC5-MHC6)
INTL          [bit set] // Transmission, ++
MHC5_INTL     [uA]      // MHC5 current at interlock
MHC6_INTL     [uA]      // MHC6 current at interlock
LOSS56_INTL   [uA]      // Losses at interlock
INTL_INTL     [bit set] // Interlock at interlock
// Inputs
SV56          [0/00]    // Expected losses
DIFF5         [uA]      // Maximum difference
EPS5          [uA]      // Maximum loss at zero current
INT_N         [cycles]  // Integration time before processing
FILTCOEFF     [cycles]  // Filter coefficient

```

```
FILTCOEFEPS    [cycles] // Epsilon of filter coefficient
NORMCURR       [uA]      // Normalized current for difference
// Integration
  if (INT_N < 1) {INT_N = 1}
// Accumulate over INT_N samples
  if ( INT_COUNT < INT_N) {
    INT_COUNT = INT_COUNT + 1
    ACC_MHC5 = ACC_MHC5 + MHC5_IN
    ACC_MHC6 = ACC_MHC6 + MHC6_IN
  } else {
// Calculate mean values over INT_N samples
    INT_COUNT = 0
    MEAN_MHC5 = ACC_MHC5 / INT_N
    MEAN_MHC6 = ACC_MHC6 / INT_N
    ACC_MHC5 = 0
    ACC_MHC6 = 0
// Calculate filter coefficient
    if (MEAN_MHC5 > OLDREFCURR) {OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC5}
    EFFILCOEF=FILTCOEF * (1 - OLDREFCURR/NORMCURR) + FILTCOEFEPS
// Compensate stored filter sum for new filter coefficient
    K1 = OLDEFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K1 <= 1.0) {K1 = 1.0}
    K2 = EFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K2 <= 1.0) {
      K2 = 1.0
      EFFILCOEF = 2.0
    }
// Store old state for next calculation
    OLDEFFILCOEF = EFFILCOEF
    OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC5
// Calculate digital filter for MHC5
    DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 + MEAN_MHC5
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC5 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 - OUT
    MHC5 = OUT
// Calculate digital filter for MHC6
    DF_SUM_MHC6 = DF_SUM_MHC6 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC6 = DF_SUM_MHC6 + MEAN_MHC6
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC6 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC6 = DF_SUM_MHC6 - OUT
    MHC6 = OUT
// Calculate losses
    LOSS56 = MHC5 - MHC6
    MAX_LOSS = EPS5 + DIFF5 * MHC5 / NORMCURR
// Correct for splitter losses
    EFF_LOSS = MHC5 - MHC6 - SV56 * MHC5 / 1000.0
// Check if losses are within limit
    if (LOSS >= 0.0) {
```

```

        if (EFF_LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B56 = 1      }
    } else {
        if (-EFF_LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B56N = 1}
    }
// First interlock and timer logic
    if (INTL and timer == 0) {
// Start the timer
        timer = 1
// Copy interlock state
        MHC5_INTL = MHC5
        MHC6_INTL = MHC6
        LOSS56_INTL = LOSS56
        INTL_INTL = INTL
    } elseif (timer > TIMEOUT_65MS) {
// Reset timer, interlock output and digital filter at beam ramp-down
        timer = 0
        INTL.B56 = 0
        INTL.B56N = 0
        DF_SUM_MHC5 = 0
        DF_SUM_MHC6 = 0
    } else {
// Do nothing during 65ms
        timer = timer + 1
    }
}
}

```

4.11.2 Transmissions Slot#2

STRAM assembler files used for defining slot#2 transmissions:

| ASM-File | Currents | EPICS Name |
|---------------|-------------|------------|
| TRANS3H1.ASM: | MNC3, MHC1B | MNTR |

4.11.2.1 TRANS3H1.ASM (MNTR)

```

// Outputs
MNC3          [uA]      // Digitized MNC3 current from MESTRA
MHC1          [uA]      // Digitized MHC1 current from MESTRA
LOSS31        [uA]      // Calculated losses (MNC3-MHC1)
INTL          [bit set] // Transmission, ++
MNC3_INTL     [uA]      // MNC3 current at interlock
MHC1_INTL     [uA]      // MHC1 current at interlock
LOSS31_INTL   [uA]      // Losses at interlock
INTL_INTL     [bit set] // Interlock at interlock
// Inputs
SV31          [0/00]    // Expected losses
DIFF5         [uA]      // Maximum difference
EPS5          [uA]      // Maximum loss at zero current
INT_N         [cycles]  // Integration time before processing

```

```
FILTCOEF      [cycles] // Filter coefficient
FILTCOEFEPS   [cycles] // Epsilon of filter coefficient
NORMCURR      [uA]      // Normalized current for difference
// Integration
  if (INT_N < 1) {INT_N = 1}
// Accumulate over INT_N samples
  if ( INT_COUNT < INT_N) {
    INT_COUNT = INT_COUNT + 1
    ACC_MNC3 = ACC_MNC3 + MNC3_IN
    ACC_MHC1 = ACC_MHC1 + MHC1_IN
  } else {
// Calculate mean values over INT_N samples
    INT_COUNT = 0
    MEAN_MNC3 = ACC_MNC3 / INT_N
    MEAN_MHC1 = ACC_MHC1 / INT_N
    ACC_MNC3 = 0
    ACC_MHC1 = 0
// Calculate filter coefficient
    if (MEAN_MNC3 > OLDREFCURR) {OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MNC3}
    EFFILCOEF=FILTCOEF * (1 - OLDREFCURR/NORMCURR) + FILTCOEFEPS
// Compensate stored filter sum for new filter coefficient
    K1 = OLDEFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K1 <= 1.0) {K1 = 1.0}
    K2 = EFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K2 <= 1.0) {
      K2 = 1.0
      EFFILCOEF = 2.0
    }
// Store old state for next calculation
    OLDEFFILCOEF = EFFILCOEF
    OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MNC3
// Calculate digital filter for MNC3
    DF_SUM_MNC3 = DF_SUM_MNC3 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MNC3 = DF_SUM_MNC3 + MEAN_MNC3
    OUT = DF_SUM_MNC3 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MNC3 = DF_SUM_MNC3 - OUT
    MNC3 = OUT
// Calculate digital filter for MHC1
    DF_SUM_MHC1 = DF_SUM_MHC1 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC1 = DF_SUM_MHC1 + MEAN_MHC1
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC1 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC1 = DF_SUM_MHC1 - OUT
    MHC1 = OUT
// Calculate losses
    LOSS31 = MNC3 - MHC1
    MAX_LOSS = EPS5 + DIFF5 * MNC3 / NORMCURR
// Correct for splitter losses
    EFF_LOSS = MNC3 - MHC1 - SV31 * MNC3 / 1000.0
// Check if losses are within limit
```

```

    if (LOSS >= 0.0) {
        if (EFF_LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B31 = 1      }
    } else {
        if (-EFF_LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B31N = 1}
    }
// First interlock and timer logic
    if (INTL and timer == 0) {
// Start the timer
        timer = 1
// Copy interlock state
        MNC3_INTL = MNC3
        MHC1_INTL = MHC1
        LOSS31_INTL = LOSS31
        INTL_INTL = INTL
    } elseif (timer > TIMEOUT_65MS) {
// Reset timer, interlock output and digital filter at beam ramp-down
        timer = 0
        INTL.B31 = 0
        INTL.B31N = 0
        DF_SUM_MNC3 = 0
        DF_SUM_MHC1 = 0
    } else {
// Do nothing during 65ms
        timer = timer + 1
    }
}
}

```

4.11.3 Transmissions Slot#3

STRAM assembler files used for defining slot#3 transmissions:

| ASM-File | Currents | EPICS Name |
|---------------|-----------|------------|
| TRANS4Q5.ASM: | MHC4,MHC5 | MHTR2-M |

NOTE: No software calibration for TRANS4Q5.ASM allowed. Tuning is done with hardware attenuators.

4.11.3.1 TRANS4Q5.ASM (MHTR2-M)

```

// Outputs
    MHC4          [uA]      // Digitized MBC4 current from MESTRA
    MHC5          [uA]      // Digitized MBC5 current from MESTRA
    TRANS45      [0/00]    // Calculated transmission MHC5/MHC4
    INTL          [bit set] // Transmission, ++
    MHC4_INTL    [uA]      // MHC4 current at interlock
    MHC5_INTL    [uA]      // MHC5 current at interlock
    TRANS45_INTL [0/00]    // Transmission MHC5/MHC4 at interlock
    INTL_INTL    [bit set] // Interlock at interlock
// Inputs - fixed in production firmware

```

```
SV45          [0/00]    // Expected losses MHC4-5
SVI45         [0/00/uA] // Expected losses current dep. MHC4-5
DIFF4         [uA]      // Maximum losses MHC4-MHC5
EPS4          [uA]      // Maximum loss at zero current
INT_N         [cycles]  // Integration time before processing
FILTCOEFF     [cycles]  // Filter coefficient
FILTCOEFEPS   [cycles]  // Epsilon of filter coefficient
NORMCURR      [uA]      // Normalized current for difference
IIMIN         [uA]      // Minimum current for interlock check

// Integration
  if (INT_N < 1) {INT_N = 1}
// Accumulate over INT_N samples
  if ( INT_COUNT < INT_N) {
    INT_COUNT = INT_COUNT + 1
    ACC_MHC4 = ACC_MHC4 + MHC4_IN
    ACC_MHC5 = ACC_MHC5 + MHC5_IN
  } else {
// Calculate mean values over INT_N samples
    INT_COUNT = 0
    MEAN_MHC4 = ACC_MHC4 / INT_N
    MEAN_MHC5 = ACC_MHC5 / INT_N
    ACC_MHC4 = 0
    ACC_MHC5 = 0
// Calculate filter coefficient
    if (MEAN_MHC4 > OLDREFCURR) {OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC4}
    EFFILCOEF = FILTCOEFF * (1 - OLDREFCURR/NORMCURR) + FILTCOEFEPS
// Compensate stored filter sum for new filter coefficient
    K1 = OLDEFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K1 <= 1.0) {K1 = 1.0}
    K2 = EFFILCOEF - 1.0
    if (K2 <= 1.0) {
      K2 = 1.0
      EFFILCOEF = 2.0
    }
// Store old state for next calculation
    OLDEFFILCOEF = EFFILCOEF
    OLDREFCURR = MEAN_MHC4
// Calculate digital filter for MHC4
    DF_SUM_MHC4 = DF_SUM_MHC4 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC4 = DF_SUM_MHC4 + MEAN_MHC4
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC4 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC4 = DF_SUM_MHC4 - OUT
    MHC4 = OUT
// Calculate digital filter for MHC5
    DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 / K1 * K2
    DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 + MEAN_MHC5
    OUT = DF_SUM_MHC5 / EFFILCOEF
    DF_SUM_MHC5 = DF_SUM_MHC5 - OUT
    MHC5 = OUT
```

```
// Calculate losses MHC4-MHC5
MAX_LOSS = EPS4 + DIFF4 * MHC4 / NORMCURR
LOSS = MHC4 * (1000.0 - SV45 - (MHC4 * SVI45 / 1600)) / 1000.0
      - MHC5
if (MHC4 > IIMIN) {
  if (LOSS >= 0.0) {
    if (LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B45 = 1    }
  } else {
    if (-LOSS > MAX_LOSS) {INTL.B45N = 1}
  }
}
// Calculate transmission MHC5/MHC4
if (MHC4 < 1.0) {
  TRANS45 = 0.0
} else {
  TRANS45 = MHC5 * 1000.0 / MHC4
}
// First interlock and timer logic
if (INTL and timer == 0) {
// Start the timer
  timer = 1
// Copy interlock state
  MHC4_INTL = MHC4
  MHC5_INTL = MHC5
  TRANS45_INTL = TRANS45
// Set interlock output
  INTL = 1
  } elseif (timer > TIMEOUT_65MS) {
// Reset timer, interlock output and digital filter at beam ramp-down
  timer = 0
  INTL.B45 = 0
  INTL.B45N = 0
  DF_SUM_MHC2 = 0
  DF_SUM_MHC3 = 0
  DF_SUM_MHC4 = 0
  DF_SUM_MHC5 = 0
  } else {
// Do nothing during 65ms
  timer = timer + 1
}
```

5 Commissioning

5.1 EtherCAT CoE Static Configuration

EL2521 factory setting has a base frequency 1 of 50000Hz. The frequency factor has to be set to 10Hz/digit and the module is turned into direct mode with the CoE (CAN over EtherCAT) protocol. This is done during commissioning of the modules and the parameter is stored in EEPROM. This is done with the IgH ethercat tool (ethercat download). This allows the frequency process variable to set the frequency in the range of 0 to 327,67kHz in 10Hz steps (frequency setting is signed so max value is 32767).

NOTE: Module requires reboot to activate the parameter change.

| Index | Subindex | Value | Description |
|--------|----------|--------------|------------------------------------|
| 0x8000 | 0x06 | 0x00 | Ramp function deactivated |
| 0x8000 | 0x08 | 0x01 | Direct frequency mode |
| 0x8001 | 0x06 | 0x3E8 (1000) | Frequency factor equals 10Hz/digit |

Table 19 EL2521 CoE Settings

All other EtherCAT terminals may remain with factory settings and do not require CoE configuration.

5.2 Preamplifier tuning

The preamplifier has a fixed amplification of approx. +25dB (some channels +50dB). The power-level must be tuned to fit the +10dBm maximum power-level of the ADC input. This is done with fixed external attenuators. Tuning setting is defined as max +8dBm at 3mA beam current.

For the parallel operation the cavity test-input is used as output. For cavities where A and B signal is used a passive two-way power-splitter (-6dB) is used for signal distribution of the test-signal.

5.3 System Startup

At system startup the controllers (IFC1210) are scanning the EtherCAT network. For successful boot procedure it is required that all EtherCAT modules are turned on **before** booting the controllers.

After successful controller boot EtherCAT modules may be replaced without reboot.

5.4 EtherCAT Debugging

Debugging of the EtherCAT slaves is done by logging onto the IFC1210 controllers and use the ethercat utility. Password is "root".

```
ssh root@ZPSAF66-VMEIFC
```

```
root@ZPSAF66-VMEIFC:/ioc/ZPSAF66-VMEIFC# ethercat slaves
0 0:0 OP + EK1100 EtherCAT-Koppler (2A E-Bus)
1 0:1 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
2 0:2 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
3 0:3 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
4 0:4 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
5 0:5 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
6 0:6 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
7 0:7 OP + EL3314 4K. Ana. Eingang Thermoelement (TC)
8 0:8 PREOP + EL9410 E-Bus Netzteilklemme (Diagnose)
9 0:9 OP + EL2521 1K. Pulse Train Ausgang
10 0:10 OP + EL2521 1K. Pulse Train Ausgang
11 0:11 OP + EL2521 1K. Pulse Train Ausgang
12 0:12 OP + EL2521 1K. Pulse Train Ausgang
13 0:13 PREOP + EL9410 E-Bus Netzteilklemme (Diagnose)
14 0:14 PREOP + EK1521 1-Port EtherCAT-Abzweig (FX-MultiMode)
15 0:15 PREOP + EK1501 EtherCAT-Koppler (2A E-Bus, FX-MultiMode, ID-Switch)
16 0:16 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
17 0:17 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
18 0:18 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
19 0:19 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
20 0:20 PREOP + EK1521 1-Port EtherCAT-Abzweig (FX-MultiMode)
21 0:21 PREOP + EK1501 EtherCAT-Koppler (2A E-Bus, FX-MultiMode, ID-Switch)
22 0:22 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
23 0:23 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
24 0:24 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
25 0:25 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
26 0:26 PREOP + EK1521 1-Port EtherCAT-Abzweig (FX-MultiMode)
27 0:27 PREOP + EK1501 EtherCAT-Koppler (2A E-Bus, FX-MultiMode, ID-Switch)
28 0:28 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
29 0:29 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
30 0:30 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
31 0:31 OP + EL4102 2K. Ana. Ausgang 0-10V, 16bit
32 0:32 OP + EL9505 Netzteilklemme 5V
33 0:33 OP + EL1124 4K. Dig. Eingang 5V, 10mA, Sensorversorgung
34 0:34 OP + EL2124 4K. Dig. Ausgang 5V, 20mA
```

6 Appendix

6.1 System Specifications

| Parameter | Description | Min | Typical | Max | Units |
|-----------|--|----------|----------|----------|---------|
| CAL_IN | RF calibration power level at 3000uA beam current | | 8 | | dBm |
| RF_IN | Maximum RF input power level at ADC3110 | | 10 | | dBm |
| BEAM_CUR | Beam current sensitivity | 1 | | 3000 | μ A |
| BEAM_MIN | Beam current zero threshold | | 0.2 | | μ A |
| BEAM_RES | Beam current resolution | | 0.1 | | μ A |
| RF_HZ | RF input frequency | 101.2646 | 101.2656 | 101.2666 | MHz |
| ADC_HZ | ADC sample rate | | 50.000 | | MHz |
| DDC_HZ | DDC Bandwidth | | 18 | | kHz |
| EC_HZ | EtherCAT Sample Rate | | 5 | | kHz |
| V_OUT | Voltage output scaling
(max 2.5mA beam current for compatibility) | | 4 | | V/mA |
| F_OUT | Frequency output scaling | | 100 | | kHz/mA |

Table 20 Measurement Specifications

| Position | Slot# | Type | Database Name | Description |
|----------|-------|---------|----------------|------------------------------|
| S1 | 1 | IFC1210 | ZPSAF66-VMEIFC | MESTRA A controller |
| S1.FMC1 | 1 | ADC3110 | - | 8 RF input channels |
| S2 | 2 | IFC1210 | ZPSAF67-VMEIFC | MESTRA B controller |
| S2.FMC1 | 2 | ADC3110 | - | 8 RF input channels |
| S3 | 3 | IFC1210 | ZPSAF68-VMEIFC | MESTRA C controller |
| S3.FMC1 | 3 | ADC3110 | - | 8 RF input channels |
| S4 | 4 | IFC1210 | ZPSAF73-VMEIFC | MESTRA D controller |
| S4.FMC1 | 4 | ADC3110 | - | 8 RF input channels (spares) |
| S5 | 5 | IFC1210 | ZPSAF74-VMEIFC | MESTRA E controller |
| S5.FMC1 | 5 | ADC3110 | - | 8 RF input channels (spares) |
| - | 6 | Empty | - | |
| - | 7 | Empty | - | |

Table 21 Crate Slot Assignment

| Cavity | IN | OUT Gain |
|--------|----|----------|
| MHC1 | 1 | +25dB |
| MHC2 | 2 | +25dB |
| MBC1 | 3 | +25dB |
| MBC1B | 4 | +25dB |
| MHC3 | 5 | +25dB |
| MHC4 | 6 | +25dB |
| MHC5 | 7 | +25dB |
| MHC6 | 8 | +25dB |
| MXC1 | 9 | +25dB |
| MXC2 | 10 | +25dB |
| Spare | 11 | +25dB |
| MNC3 | 12 | +25dB |
| MHC1B | 13 | +25dB |
| MYC1 | 14 | +50dB |
| MYC2 | 15 | +50dB |
| Spare | 16 | +50dB |

Table 22 Analog Input Assignment Preamplifier (PA1)

| Cavity | IN | OUT Gain |
|--------|----|----------|
| Spare | 1 | +25dB |
| Spare | 2 | +25dB |
| Spare | 3 | +25dB |
| Spare | 4 | +25dB |
| Spare | 5 | +25dB |
| MHC4 | 6 | +25dB |
| MHC5 | 7 | +25dB |
| Spare | 8 | +25dB |
| Spare | 9 | +25dB |
| Spare | 10 | +25dB |
| Spare | 11 | +25dB |
| Spare | 12 | +25dB |
| Spare | 13 | +25dB |
| Spare | 14 | +50dB |
| Spare | 15 | +50dB |
| Spare | 16 | +50dB |

Table 23 Analog Input Assignment Preamplifier (PA2)

| IFC1210
Slot# | ADC3110 FMC1
CH | Cavity |
|------------------|--------------------|--------|
| 1 | 0 | MHC1 |
| 1 | 1 | MHC2 |
| 1 | 2 | MBC1 |
| 1 | 3 | MBC1B |
| 1 | 4 | MHC3 |
| 1 | 5 | MHC4 |
| 1 | 6 | MHC5 |
| 1 | 7 | MHC6 |
| 2 | 0 | MXC1 |
| 2 | 1 | MXC2 |
| 2 | 2 | Spare |
| 2 | 3 | MNC3 |
| 2 | 4 | MHC1B |
| 2 | 5 | MYC1 |
| 2 | 6 | MYC2 |
| 2 | 7 | NC |
| 3 | 0 | NC |
| 3 | 1 | NC |
| 3 | 2 | NC |
| 3 | 3 | NC |
| 3 | 4 | NC |
| 3 | 5 | MHC4-2 |
| 3 | 6 | MHC5-2 |
| 3 | 7 | NC |

Table 24 Analog Input Assignment ADC3110 (S1.FMC1/S2.FMC1/S3.FMC1)

6.2 Cable List

| Subsystem | Description | Cable Name | From | To | Length [m] | Type |
|---------------|-----------------------|------------|--------|----------|------------|---------------|
| Cavity Cables | | | | | | |
| MHC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC1.A | T.MHC1.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC1.B | T.MHC1.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC1.T | T.MHC1.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC2.A | T.MHC2.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC2.B | T.MHC2.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC2.T | T.MHC2.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MBC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MBC1.A | T.MBC1.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MBC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MBC1.B | T.MBC1.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MBC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MBC1.T | T.MBC1.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC3 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC3.A | T.MHC3.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC3 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC3.B | T.MHC3.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC3 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC3.T | T.MHC3.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC4 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC4.A | T.MHC4.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC4 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC4.B | T.MHC4.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC4 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC4.T | T.MHC4.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC5 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC5.A | T.MHC5.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC5 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC5.B | T.MHC5.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC5 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC5.T | T.MHC5.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC6 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC6.A | T.MHC6.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC6 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC6.B | T.MHC6.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MHC6 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MHC6.T | T.MHC6.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MXC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MXC1.A | T.MXC1.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MXC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MXC1.B | T.MXC1.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MXC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MXC1.T | T.MXC1.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MXC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MXC2.A | T.MXC2.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MXC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MXC2.B | T.MXC2.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MXC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MXC2.T | T.MXC2.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MNC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MNC1.A | T.MNC1.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MNC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MNC1.B | T.MNC1.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MNC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MNC1.T | T.MNC1.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MNC3 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MNC3.A | T.MNC3.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MNC3 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MNC3.B | T.MNC3.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MNC3 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MNC3.T | T.MNC3.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MYC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MYC1.A | T.MYC1.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MYC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MYC1.B | T.MYC1.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MYC1 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MYC1.T | T.MYC1.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MYC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MYC2.A | T.MYC2.A | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MYC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MYC2.B | T.MYC2.B | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| MYC2 | Cellflex cavity cable | | MYC2.T | T.MYC2.T | | LCF12-50J N-N |
| | | | | Sum | 0 | |

| EtherCAT Electrical Cables | | | | | | |
|----------------------------|------------------------------|--|--------------------------|----------------------------------|---|-------------|
| EtherCAT | Ethernet cable | | EC1.P0.X1 | S1.IFC.ETH1 | 1 | CAT6 RJ45 |
| EtherCAT | Ethernet cable | | EC2.P0.X1 | S2.IFC.ETH1 | 1 | CAT6 RJ45 |
| EtherCAT Optical Cables | | | | | | |
| EtherCAT | Fibre optical junction cable | | EC1.P7.X1
WBGA B11.12 | EC1.0.P0.X1
WEHA E23.8 | | 50/125um SC |
| EtherCAT | Fibre optical junction cable | | EC1.P8.X1
WBGA B11.12 | EC1.1.P0.X1
WNHA
NA2.13.49 | | 50/125um SC |
| EtherCAT | Fibre optical junction cable | | EC1.P9.X1
WBGA B11.12 | EC1.2.P0.X1
??? | | 50/125um SC |
| EtherCAT | Fibre optical junction cable | | EC2.P7.X1
WBGA B11.12 | EC2.0.P0.X1
WIHA/EG
G48.1 | | 50/125um SC |
| EtherCAT | Fibre optical junction cable | | EC2.P8.X1
WBGA B11.12 | EC2.1.P0.X1
WSGA/OG
S87.12 | | 50/125um SC |
| EtherCAT | Fibre optical junction cable | | EC2.P9.X1
WBGA B11.12 | EC2.2.P0.X1
??? | | 50/125um SC |
| | | | | Sum | 2 | |
| Preamplifier Cables | | | | | | |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MHC1.A | PA.IN1 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MHC2.A | PA.IN2 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MBC1.A | PA.IN3 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MBC1.B | PA.IN4 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MHC3.A | PA.IN5 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MHC4.A | PA.IN6 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MHC5.A | PA.IN7 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MHC6.A | PA.IN8 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MXC1.A | PA.IN9 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MXC2.A | PA.IN10 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MNC1.A | PA.IN11 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MNC3.A | PA.IN12 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MHC1.B | PA.IN13 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MYC1.A | PA.IN14 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Terminal to preamp cable | | T.MYC2.A | PA.IN15 | 2 | N-SMA |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT1 | S1.FMC1.CH0 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT2 | S1.FMC1.CH1 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT3 | S1.FMC1.CH2 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT4 | S1.FMC1.CH3 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT5 | S1.FMC1.CH4 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT6 | S1.FMC1.CH5 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT7 | S1.FMC1.CH6 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT8 | S1.FMC1.CH7 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT9 | S2.FMC1.CH0 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT10 | S2.FMC1.CH1 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |

| | | | | | | |
|--------------|---------------------|--|----------|-------------|---|----------|
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT11 | S2.FMC1.CH2 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT12 | S2.FMC1.CH3 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT13 | S2.FMC1.CH4 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT14 | S2.FMC1.CH5 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |
| Preamplifier | Preamp to ADC cable | | PA.OUT15 | S2.FMC1.CH6 | 1 | SMA-SSMC |

Table 25 Cable List

Legend

- T. Terminal in WBGA B11.12
- PA. Preamplifier in WBGA B11.12
- S1. Slot1 in WBGA B11.12
- S2. Slot2 in WBGA B11.12
- Px. EtherCAT Position
- EC1. EtherCAT Slot1 in WBGA B11.12
- EC2. EtherCAT Slot2 in WBGA B11.12
- EC3. EtherCAT Slot3 in WBGA B11.12

6.3 Spare Parts

- Two IFC1210 with ADC3110 (preconfigured)
- One Preamplifier
- One EtherCAT I/O Local Block
- One EtherCAT I/O Remote Block
- One MM optical fiber (max. length)

6.4 Cost Estimation

| Subsystem | Description | Units | Cost/Unit | Sum | Units |
|-----------|-------------------------------------|-------|--------------|---------------|------------|
| Crate | Trenew 118164 7-slot crate | 1 | 2300 | 2300 | CHF |
| Crate | IFC1210 Intelligent FPGA controller | 5 | 4500 | 22500 | CHF |
| Crate | ADC3110 16-bit FMC ADC-card | 5 | 3000 | 15000 | CHF |
| Preamp | Custom amplifiers | 2 | 5000 | 10000 | CHF |
| EtherCAT | Coupler, Terminals | 200 | 150 | 30000 | CHF |
| Cables | SMA-SSMC | 16 | 45 | 720 | CHF |
| Cables | Fibre optical MM-SC cable | 8 | 400 | 3200 | CHF |
| Spares | Div | 1 | 25000 | 25000 | CHF |
| | | | Total | 108720 | CHF |

Table 26 Cost Estimation - Material

6.5 Source Directories

| Directory | Description |
|---|---|
| https://codebeamer.psi.ch/svn/IFC_SourceCode/IFC/IFC1210_applications/Diagnostics/DDC/Software/mestra_a | Linux stand-alone applications for calculating currents and transmission for slot#1 |
| https://codebeamer.psi.ch/svn/IFC_SourceCode/IFC/IFC1210_applications/Diagnostics/DDC/Software/mestra_b | Linux stand-alone applications for calculating currents and transmission for slot#2 |
| https://codebeamer.psi.ch/svn/IFC_SourceCode/IFC/IFC1210_applications/Diagnostics/DDC/Software/mestra_c | Linux stand-alone applications for calculating currents and transmission for slot#3 |
| https://codebeamer.psi.ch/svn/IFC_SourceCode/IFC/IFC1210_applications/Diagnostics/DDC/Software/mestra_d | Linux stand-alone applications for distributing signals to experiments slot#4 |
| https://codebeamer.psi.ch/svn/IFC_SourceCode/IFC/IFC1210_applications/Diagnostics/DDC/Software/mestra_e | L Linux stand-alone applications for distributing signals to experiments slot#5 |
| https://codebeamer.psi.ch/svn/IFC_SourceCode/IFC/IFC1210_applications/Diagnostics/DDC/Firmware | IFC1210 Central FPGA application with DDC circuit for ADC_3110 in slot FMC1. |
| Z/DI/MESTRA in repository
:pserver:Johansen@slscvs02.psi.ch:/cvs | Production EPICS and Qt configuration files |

Table 27 Source Directories

6.6 Document History

| Status | Author | Date | Description |
|--------|----------------|------------|---|
| Draft | Ernst Johansen | 30.06.2015 | Working Draft |
| Draft | Ernst Johansen | 22.10.2015 | Review with Urban Frei |
| Draft | Ernst Johansen | 21.07.2016 | Added Megapie transmission in slot#3 |
| Draft | Ernst Johansen | 07.04.2017 | Changed application links to toasca version |
| Draft | Ernst Johansen | 04.09.2017 | Changed to Rev B with Experiment support |
| Draft | Ernst Johansen | 12.09.2017 | Changed to Rev C with Experiment support and two additional IFC1210 |
| Draft | Ernst Johansen | 16.10.2017 | Changed to two remote EtherCAT blocks for RF (third removed) |
| | | | |

Table 28 Document History